

PSDI
PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

D | C | C
CCDC

Exploring Data Curation and Management in the Physical Sciences

Cambridge Roadshow
25 June 2025

The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre

Dedicated to the advancement of chemistry and crystallography for the public benefit through high quality information services and software.

We:

- **Curate** and disseminate 3D structural data worldwide through the CSD
- **Deliver** knowledge-based solutions to accelerate the discovery and development of new medicines and materials.
- **Promote** research collaboration to advance structural science.
- **Inspire** a new generation of structural chemists through outreach and education.

Not-for-profit Registered Charity number 800579. Staff primarily based in the UK and in the US.

CCDC

The Cambridge Structural Database

- Over 1.3 Million small-molecule organic and metal-organic crystal structures
- Around 80,000 structures deposited annually, many associated with journal articles
- Structures from Patents, Theses and *CSD Communications* also

Inside the Cambridge Structural Database

4

A comprehensive database of published organic and metal-organic experimental crystal structures

Organic
45%

Metal-Organic
55%

At least one transition metal,
lanthanide, actinide or any of Al,
Ga, In, Tl, Ge, Sn, Pb, Sb, Bi, Po

Organic

- Drugs
- Agrochemicals
- Pigments
- Explosives
- Protein ligands

Additional data

- 14,019 polymorph families
- 176,704 melting points
- 1,127,300 crystal colours
- 1,005,205 crystal shapes
- 32,100 bioactivity details
- 14,344 natural source data
- > 400,000 oxidation states

Not Polymeric
88%

Polymeric: 12%

Metal-Organic

- Metal Organic Frameworks
- Models for new catalysts
- Porous frameworks for gas storage
- Fundamental chemical bonding

Single
Component
58%

Multi
Component
42%

Links and subsets

- DrugBank
- Druglike
- MOFs
- PDB ligands
- PubChem
- ChemSpider
- Pesticide PDB

Roadshow Outline

10:00 – 10:30	Welcome and introductions
10:30 – 11:25	Perspectives on curating and publishing data
11:25 – 11:40	<i>Coffee and networking break</i>
11:40 – 12:40	Further perspectives and lightning talks
12:40 – 13:25	<i>Networking lunch</i>
13:25 – 13:40	A crystallographic perspective
13:40 – 16:10	Interactive sessions
16:10 – 16:25	Next steps and closing remarks

PSDI

PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Introduction to the Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI)

Data Curation Roadshow - Cambridge
25th June 2025

<https://www.psd.ac.uk/>

Presentation Outline

- ▶ What is PSDI
- ▶ A sample of PSDI Offerings
- ▶ Getting involved with PSDI

What is PSDI?

- ▶ UK funded project through the UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure theme (DRI) via EPSRC
- ▶ Developed out of a community statement of need
- ▶ Lead institutions: University of Southampton and Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC)
- ▶ First launch of resources are now live!

Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure

An Integrated Data Infrastructure for the Physical Sciences

PSDI aims to accelerate research in the physical sciences by providing a data infrastructure that brings together and builds upon the various data systems researchers currently use.

www.psd.ac.uk

Drivers for PSDI: Barriers & Challenges for the Physical Sciences

Data

- ▶ Lack of access to reusable structured datasets
 - ▶ Un-FAIR Data
- ▶ Data locked away in proprietary formats
- ▶ Lack of metadata / provenance
- ▶ Cost of storing data

Technology

- ▶ Too many (and yet not enough) formats and standards
- ▶ Complexity in selecting and adhering to standards
- ▶ Lack of interoperability between software

People

- ▶ Attitude and adoption of standards and principles
 - ▶ Lack of knowledge and skills around data management (need data stewards!)
- ▶ Lack of time and human resource

The Aim

PSDI will provide

A data infrastructure that
connects existing
experimental and computational facilities
within Physical Sciences and beyond

A platform for data
collection, sharing,
aggregation, integration
and curation

Supporting analysis
across experimental,
simulation and
reference data

Combining and
enhancing existing data
infrastructures

Sustaining data
resources beyond
lifespan of individual
research projects

Diverse Pathfinders driving requirements

What can PSDI do for you?

Data Services

Data Tools

Community

Access to
Data Sources

Guidance,
Training &
Case Studies

Collaboration

Find our resources on www.psd.ac.uk!

Access to Data

Over 30 different data sources

Including:

- ▶ Cambridge Structural Database (CSD)
- ▶ Propersea (Property Prediction)
- ▶ Chemical Availability Search (ChASe)
- ▶ Chemotion
- ▶ STFC Open Data

Data Revival Service

PSDI is providing a free version of the Data Revival Software

- ▶ This can be used to scan your handwritten lab book pages and turn them into machine-readable data
- ▶ Remember: Even if you implement digital notetaking tomorrow, there will still be a considerable amount of legacy data that may require digitisation

Scan in paper
lab notebook
pages

Convert into
machine-
readable
content

Relational
links across
chemistry
data

Semantic
Search

High degree
of accuracy

Data Format Conversion Service

We have created a service to address the issue of Interoperability in the Physical Sciences

- ▶ Ultimate goal: One stop shop for data conversion – without the need to write complicated code or download and test many converters
- ▶ Provide information about conversions and potential quality issues e.g. loss of information

Extensive
Format
Support

Multiple
Converters

Seamless
Customisable
Conversion

Accessibility

Multiple
mechanisms
of use

Reproducible Scientific Workflows

- ▶ Often papers don't contain enough detail to allow simulation or analysis to be repeated
- ▶ We're developing tools to capture the full data provenance in a scientific workflow

Link data and models to results and publications

Simple for researchers!

Support multiple workflow systems

Visualise the provenance for calculations

Allow users to store their provenance archives

- ▶ Initial Focus areas: Biomolecular simulations, machine learnt interatomic potentials, muon experiments, X-Ray absorption spectroscopy

Knowledge Base

- ▶ The PSDI Knowledge Base will provide guidance for physical scientists, and those who support them, about a range of topics related to research data and PSDI technology and resources.

- ▶ A growing collection of content that can be built with the community.

Case Studies

- ▶ To supplement our guidance, we are also producing case studies to help the community, ranging from implementing new tools to curating legacy data

- ▶ If you have existing case studies or ideas for new ones please get in touch!

Training Activities

PSDI is committed to upskilling the physical sciences community, and we offer a range of training activities

- ▶ Self Paced Learning Resources
- ▶ In Person Training
 - ▶ Training Workshops
 - ▶ Skills4Scientists Intern Training
 - ▶ Machine Learning Summer Schools
- ▶ Tutorials
- ▶ Webinars

DATA PUBLISHING	
GOOD	BAD
DATA REPOSITORY	STICKY NOTE ON YOUR DOOR
INSTITUTIONAL ARCHIVE	SUPPLEMENTARY DATA
	BOTTOM OF A WELL

AI4SD
ERRANTSCIENCE.COM

Community

Not just about technology Channel with Publishers

Internships & Placements

Advocacy

Community
workshops & forums

Identify Skills Gaps

**Research
Culture**

Channel with Funders

Requirements gathering

Champions

Policy Design & Implementation

Community of
Practice

Validation of ideas

**Sharing Best
Practice**

**Data skills
training**

Provision of
guidance

Community Involvement

CaSDaR
Careers and Skills for
Data-driven Reserach

ELN Finder

RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

I U P A C

INTERNATIONAL UNION OF
PURE AND APPLIED CHEMISTRY

InChI TRUST

WorldFAIR

CCDC
advancing structural science

NFDI₄Chem

BEILSTEIN INSTITUT

NFDI₄Cat

NFDI for Catalysis-Related Sciences

IUCr
International Union
of Crystallography

If you want to get involved with PSDI contact psdi@soton.ac.uk!

Got an idea to solve a data problem?

Speak to us!

You can reach the team through
psdi@soton.ac.uk and
we will connect you

Find out more about PSDI

 www.psd.ac.uk

 PSDIUK

 @PSDI_UK

 @psdi-uk.bsky.social

 @PSDI@mstdn.science

 @PSDI_UK

 PSDI zenodo community

Join our mailing list!

<https://www.jiscmail.ac.uk/PSDI>

PSDI

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DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Roadshow Context

How can PSDI best support
Data Curation in the Physical
Sciences?

Background

- ▶ As partners of the PSDI project, DCC and CCDC are aiming to identify recommendations for **how PSDI can and should support data curation needs of UK Physical Sciences communities**
- ▶ **Areas we anticipate exploring are:**
 - ▶ The extent to which existing guidance, tools and services support current and future data curation needs
 - ▶ Data curation requirements specific to the physical sciences that go beyond general data requirements
 - ▶ How PSDI could help address unmet needs whether through guidance, tools, training, active curation or collaboration

Current Report Outline

- ▶ **What is Data Curation?!**
 - ▶ How it fits in the research lifecycle
 - ▶ Curation vs management vs preservation
- ▶ **Roles and Responsibilities**
 - ▶ What do we need from various stakeholders? Where might stakeholders need help?
- ▶ **Community Benchmarks**
 - ▶ Expectations of e.g. CoreTrustSeal
- ▶ **Available guidelines on best practice**
 - ▶ Domain-agnostic vs domain-specific
- ▶ **Case studies in the Physical Sciences**
 - ▶ Crystallography, PSDI Pathfinders, NFDI4Chem, others
- ▶ **Interoperability and integration**
 - ▶ Importance of joined-up recording and reporting workflows and platforms
- ▶ **Community needs**
 - ▶ Drawing on community engagement at curation roadshows and other events
- ▶ **Recommendations for PSDI**
 - ▶ Guidance, tools, training, services etc.

Roadshow Outline

- ▶ **Presentations**

- ▶ Perspectives on data curation and publication

- ▶ **Exercise**

- ▶ Data Management Plans in the Physical Sciences

- ▶ **Breakout discussion sessions**

- ▶ What data curation means to you
- ▶ Challenges and pain points
- ▶ Roles, responsibilities and skills
- ▶ Tools, resources and training required
- ▶ How PSDI could best help

Breakout Discussions

- ▶ **Introductions**
 - ▶ Your relationship to data curation and management
- ▶ **Discussion 1: Data Curation and Management**
 - ▶ What is data curation? What is involved?
 - ▶ How does data curation differ from / relate to data management and data preservation?
 - ▶ Main challenges and pain points?
- ▶ **Discussion 2: Roles and Responsibilities**
 - ▶ Who is responsible for data curation and data management?
 - ▶ What skills and strengths do different stakeholders offer?
 - ▶ Role of AI/Machine Learning?
 - ▶ What limitations in knowledge, tools, guidance are hindering best practice?
- ▶ **Discussion 3: What could PSDI do?**
 - ▶ How could PSDI support data curation and data management in physical sciences?
 - ▶ What tools, resources, and training are needed?

PSDI CAMBRIDGE - JUNE 25, 2025

Dryad: A case study in publishing open data across fields

Jennifer Gibson - Executive Director, Dryad
jen@datadryad.org

On today's tour:

- 1. About Dryad**
- 2. Dryad's core operational strategies**
- 3. Dryad finance**

DRYAD

Not-for-profit and online since
2008. Learn more: datadryad.org

Photo by [Alex Knight](#) on [Unsplash](#)

About Dryad

An **open data publishing platform**
& **community** committed to the
open availability and routine re-
use of all research data

- **Conceived by researchers in 2007 as home for a wide-ranging scope of data**
- **Backed by journals in 2011 with the Joint Data Archiving Policy**

👉 <https://datadryad.org/stash/about#origins>

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Institutions, publishers, and academic societies partner with Dryad to sponsor data curation, publishing, and preservation for researchers. [Learn about partnership](#)

Submit now

Most recent datasets

DFT studies of the role of anion variation in physical properties of Cs₂NaTlBr_{6-x}Cl_x (x = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6) mixed halide double perovskites for optoelectronics

Mehedi Hasan Mohammed; Nazmul Hasan; Alamgir Kabir. Halide-double perovskites have various benefits over lead-based perovskites due to their suitable optical absorption efficiency, higher stability, tunable bandgap, large carrier mobility, easy availability, and low cost. The...

Data from: Not all who wander are lost: Prospecting and settlement of male floaters in the spotless starling

Iraida Redondo; Roger Fusté; Jaime Muriel; Eduardo Gómez-Llanos; Raquel Monclús; Lorenzo Pérez-Rodríguez; Diego Gil. Floaters are non-breeding individuals that lack a territory or a breeding site. In many species, they can be seen visiting the...

How it works

Serving all research domains

Leader in research data

Interconnected

Fully curated

Login

Use your ORCID. [If your institution is a Dryad partner](#), connect to your existing credentials.

Whether or not your data are related to an article [upload your data](#) and receive

- **1,600 new submissions each month**
- **65,000+ data publications**
- **200,000+ researchers**
- **70,000+ international institutions**
- **1,270+ academic journals**

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Photo by Emma Gossett on Unsplash

Core strategies

- 1. Journal and publisher partnerships and integrations**
- 2. Institutional partnerships**
- 3. Wide disciplinary and format scope**

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2008. Learn more: datadryad.org

-
- 1. Dryad partners with journals & publishers to capture data in connection with the article publication process**

“Data are important products of the scientific enterprise, and they should be preserved and usable for decades in the future.”

 <https://datadryad.org/stash/about#origins>

“as a **condition for publication**, that **data supporting the results** in the paper should be **archived in an appropriate public archive...**”

 <https://datadryad.org/stash/about#origins>

Strengthening the scientific record

H. HOLDEN THORP, VALDA VINSON, AND JAKE YESTON [Authors Info & Affiliations](#)

SCIENCE • 30 Mar 2023 • Vol 380, Issue 6640 • p. 13 • DOI: 10.1126/science.adi0333

↓ 8,594

Science is a social process. Discoveries—even by supposed “lone” geniuses—do not become part of the scientific record until the findings are shared with the scientific community, to be vetted, challenged, and debated. Since the birth of the digital age, this discourse has become much more apparent, as digital platforms and social media lets such as social media, blogs, and websites such as PubPeer and Retraction Watch have provided a platform for the community to discuss new findings. Further, the availability of greater amounts of data and computational power allows peers to redo key analyses to confirm or report discrepancies. This week we are announcing two changes—one to accelerate the conversation about papers and another to ease deposition of supporting data—that will facilitate the evaluation of research findings across the wide

For years, the *Science* family of journals has offered Technical Comments as a mechanism for the scientific community to critique the core conclusions or methodology of research that we publish. Authors are given a chance to respond, and both the comment and response are peer-reviewed. This process was well suited to a pre-digital age. However, online platforms that support postpublication discussions are a better fit. Therefore, we are discontinuing the Technical Comments and Technical Response article types and will instead use eLetters as a forum to host comments. eLetters are submitted on our website, directly on the relevant article page, and can be posted quickly. Moreover,

In keeping with our commitment to reproducibility and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) data principles, we require all data underlying the results in published papers to be publicly and immediately available.

Questions about complying with our data access requirements arise mainly in regard to datasets that lack a corresponding field-specific repository. We are now partnering with Dryad, a nonprofit open data repository, to address this issue and simplify the process overall.

—

2. Dryad provides a robust, cost-effective –and non-profit– data-sharing solution for academic and research institutions

Institutions choose Dryad:

- As a single solution to support data-sharing for the campus, or as one of several
- To capture data independently of the publication process, and in support of funder public access policies

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Institutions choose Dryad:

- To ensure authors are well-supported and data is shared appropriately and usefully (and FAIR)
- As a cost-effective strategy
- To support non-profit and open infrastructure

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3. Dryad ensures that data from across fields is appropriate and ready to be shared and re-used

Initial submission

Upload your data, complete metadata fields, and prepare a README file. Complete the checklist and carefully review the submission before you click "Submit".

1. SUBMISSION

- Collect necessary metadata
- Link dataset to other outputs
- Ingest and validate files

Private for peer review option

When your dataset is associated with a manuscript under review, you can choose to keep the dataset private and use a temporary sharing link for peer review. The dataset can proceed to curation once the manuscript has been accepted.

Curation

Experienced data curators will thoroughly evaluate each dataset to ensure the completeness of metadata, documentation, and files, following [FAIR principles](#).

Revisions

Revise your dataset based on curator feedback. Don't hesitate to contact us with questions!

3. PUBLICATION

- Increases discoverability
- Ready links to related research objects
- Promotes data citation
- Supports versioning

Publication

After final review, our curators will approve and publish your dataset. Your DOI will become active, and your dataset will be searchable, citable, and reusable.

2. CURATION

- Supports authors from submission to publication
- Ensures data is appropriate and licensed for sharing
- Verifies data is accessible and usable
- Ensures metadata quality

Dataset submission

[Save & exit](#)

Checklist

- Title
- Authors
- Description
- Subjects
- Support
- Compliance
- Files
- README
- Related works
- Agreements

Title

Is your data used in a research article?

Yes No

 The title and other metadata can be imported from some article sources.

From what source would you like to import information?

- Submitted manuscript
- Preprint
- Published article

 If your submission is linked to an article or manuscript, sharing that information connects your data to the work. Some [partner journals](#) will also cover the [data publishing charge](#).

[◀ Previous](#)[Next ▶](#)

A descriptive title is required for your submission. The title, author list, abstract, subjects, and funders can be imported from many published articles, or from submitted manuscripts for some journals.

Dataset submission

 Save & exit

Checklist

- Title
- Authors
- Description
- Subjects
- Support
- Compliance
- Files
- README
- Related works
- Agreements

README

Your Dryad submission must be accompanied by a [README file](#), to help others use and understand your dataset. It should contain the details needed to interpret and reuse your data, including abbreviations and codes, file descriptions, and information about any necessary software.

Once you've uploaded or generated a README, you may continue to revise it in our editor.

Need to create a README?

Use our step-by-step tool to generate a README file. Some information will be imported from your uploaded files, so make sure your file list is complete.

[Build a README](#)

Already have a README file?

If you already have a README file in [markdown format](#) for your dataset, you can import it here.

[Import README](#)

 See these example READMEs from published Dryad submissions

[◀ Previous](#)[Next ▶](#)

For files and variables:

[Genomic data](#) including descriptions of data of several file types

[MATLAB files](#) described in detail

[Genomic VCF and companion scripts](#) described in detail

For code/software

Data from: Testing for unequal rates of morphological diversification in the absence of a detailed phylogeny: case study from characiform fishes

Sidlauskas, Brian ¹

Author affiliations

- 1. University of Chicago

Published Dec 17, 2007 on Dryad. <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.20>

Data files

▲ Dec 17, 2007 version files	741.88 KB
↓ Evo_22_Table_S1.doc	454.66 KB
↓ Sidlauskas_2007_Data.xls	131.58 KB
↓ Sidlauskas_2007_Landmark_Consensuses.tps	155.64 KB

Preview

Download full dataset

Citation Copy

545651 views | 176 downloads | 1 citations

Share: [in](#) [tw](#) [fb](#) [m](#) [f](#) [e](#) [g+](#)

License: [Public domain](#)

Subject keywords

[Anostomidae](#), [Anostomoidea](#), [Brownian evolution](#), [Chilodontidae](#), [Curimatoidea](#), [disparity](#), [freshwater fishes](#), [mode](#), [temp](#), [tempo](#)

Related works

Primary article From: [Evolution](#)
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1558-5646.2007.00022.x>

Abstract

This study develops the random phylogenies rate test (RAPRATE), a likelihood method that simulates morphological evolution along randomly generated phylogenies, and uses it to determine whether a considerable difference in morphological diversity between two sister clades of South American fishes should be taken as evidence of differing rates of morphological change or lineage turnover. Despite identical ages of origin, similar species richness, and sympatric geographic distributions, the morphological and ecological diversity of the superfamily Anostomoidea exceeds that of the Curimatoidea. The test shows with 90% confidence (using variance among species as the measure of morphological diversity) or 99% confidence (using volume of occupied morphospace) that the rate of morphological change per unit time in the Anostomoidea likely exceeded that of the Curimatoidea. Variation in the rate of lineage turnover (speciation and extinction rates) is not found to affect greatly the morphological diversity of simulated clades and is not a

Disambiguated identifiers (PIDs)

ORCID

ROR

DataCite

- Persistently identify: Objects, individuals, affiliations, funding, subject classification
- Facilitate dissemination and discovery across the global open research infrastructure

Citation and usage standards: Enable recognition and assessment across platforms

MAKE
DATA
COUNT

DC¹
Data Citation Principles

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Photo by [micheile henderson](#) on [Unsplash](#)

Finance

Overview

- FY26 Budget: ±\$1.5mUSD; 11 FT staff + 3 PT and freelance + outsourced business admin
- Revenue: 27% Publishing orgs; 40% Institutions; 11% Individuals; 1% IROs; 20% GREI/soft
- Dryad finances are openly available via our annual reports, form 990s, and audited financial statements - at <https://github.com/datadryad/governance/>

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Fees: Before

- Historically varied and varying
- Impossible to do long-term projections
- Tremendous burden on admin and finance
- Prone to error and omission - expensive!

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Fees: Now

- Developed by a stakeholder-based advisory group
- Based on new/recent knowledge of cost - fixed and variable
- Focuses on value as a non-profit service-provider operating in the community interest rather than as a membership organization
- Announced in March 2025, to take effect in May for new partners and January 2026 for current partners

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Fees: Now

- Combines Annual Service Fee (tiered according to partner size) and Data Publication Fee (also annual, tiered according to volume)
- Accommodates data up to 2TB, with additional fees
- Offers discounted rates for partners, compared to individuals
- Features the option to “Support” us and invest in open infrastructure and open data

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2008. Learn more: datadryad.org

Highlights from our case study

- **Researcher/user buy-in from the outset creates momentum**
- **Engagement with the publishing process is a powerful way to capture attention**
- **Multi-stakeholder participation is impactful - and hard**

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- **Broad solutions have broad appeal**
- **Approach finance with estimates of cost, rather than what can be grant-funded**
- **Please, please, please try and collaborate with existing services - and avoid compounding the challenge of sustainability for infrastructure**

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jen@datadryad.org

CAMBRIDGE
UNIVERSITY PRESS

Why research data matters to publishers

PSDI Roadshow @ Cambridge

25 June 2025

Kiera McNeice

Research Transparency Manager

Cambridge University Press and me

Cambridge:

- Non-profit publisher; a department of the University of Cambridge
- Portfolio of over 400 academic journals
- Broad range of subject areas, from dance research to fluid mechanics
- Two thirds published on behalf of external partners (e.g. learned societies)

My role:

- Advocating for and implementing best practices to support transparent, open, and reproducible research

What do publishers do?

- Cambridge's mission: "To contribute to society through the pursuit of education, learning and research at the highest international levels of excellence"
- Dissemination of research outputs that are **robust and reliable**
- Quality and integrity of publications – and the research behind them – is essential

What do our communities want?

- **Research institutions** want to maximise the impact of their researchers' work
- **Research funders** increasingly expect all outputs to be publicly accessible
- **Researchers** want to share (and get credit for!) all of their work

What does this mean for research data?

Data that underpins research publications should be available, where possible, to:

- **Reviewers**, to assess the reliability of the reported research in a publication
- **Other researchers**, to build upon results and/or collaborate with the authors
- **The general public**, to understand how conclusions were reached

...and data must be **intelligible** to all of these third parties

What is a publisher's role in all this?

- We want to ensure the research we publish is robust and reliable
- We connect reviewers with research outputs – increasingly including data
- We advise society partners on policies and practices regarding research data
- Authors (researchers) ask us where and how to share their data

An example: the journal *Political Analysis*

- Major political science journals decided in 2014 that data should be available
 - <https://www.dartstatement.org/2014-journal-editors-statement-jets>
- *PA* requires all quantitative analysis to be reproduced before publication
- Authors must share data and code in a dedicated Dataverse instance
- A dedicated Replication Editor attempts to reproduce quantitative results
- Authors may use Code Ocean to ensure their code runs for others

Challenge #1: Where should researchers share data?

- Domain-specific repositories aren't always available or known to authors
- Generalist repositories may not suit specific requirements
- Should publishers be “picking winners”? What advice should we give?
- What are the long-term plans of third parties like Dataverse and Code Ocean?

Challenge #2: It's too late to think about data when you publish

- Retrospectively cleaning, curating, and annotating data can be a massive task
- Data management needs to be baked into research projects from the start
- As a publisher, we only see one end of the research process

Challenge #3: Who reviews data?

- Peer reviewers are unpaid, often uncredited, often time-poor
- Not all journals/societies can hire a dedicated Replication Editor
 - Or pay for a third-party solution (e.g. CASCaD, the Odum Institute)
- Well-managed data, with good metadata, reduces the burden on reviewers

What helps, from a publishing perspective

- Training for all researchers on good management of data
- Clarity for researchers about where and how to share data
- Good curation and description of published data
 - ...and any repositories and services which contribute to this!

Thank you!

kiera.mcneice@cambridge.org

UNIVERSITY OF
CAMBRIDGE
Cambridge University Libraries

Research
Data

OSC
Office of Scholarly Communication

Helping researchers to be FAIR: an institutional repository perspective

Clair Castle, Research Data Manager, University of Cambridge

Email: cmc32@cam.ac.uk, [ORCID](#)

Exploring Data Curation and Management in Physical Sciences: PSDI Roadshow @ Cambridge, 25 June 2025

Today's presentation

- RDM at Cambridge
- Institutional repository, Apollo
- Physical sciences dataset deposits in Apollo
- FAIR challenges for physical sciences researchers and RDM services
- How should researchers be educated and supported in good RDM and FAIR practices?

Research Data Management at Cambridge

RDM service:

- Mediated dataset deposits into [Apollo](#), institutional repository (mainly supporting publications)
- Helpdesk
- Training
- Consultancy
- DMP review support service
- [Data Champions](#) programme oversight

Open Research Systems team manages Apollo, work closely together on technical issues

Apollo

- DSpace – open digital repository system
- Accepts most research output types
- [CoreTrustSeal](#) certified
- Apollo content received 2M+ views, +13M downloads to date
- Integrates with Elements, used to deposit research outputs into Apollo
- DOIs for research outputs (DataCite)
- Follows [FAIR](#) principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)
- Content discoverable through search engines (Google – Scholar, Datasets, Citations), indexed in re3data.org, citation databases, library catalogue (iDiscover)
- Usage and citation statistics tracked and displayed

Dataset deposits in Apollo - all disciplines, last 5 years

Physical sciences dataset deposits in Apollo - last 5 years

Observations from 2025 physical sciences deposits: file formats, software, data type (~70)

- Lots of data deriving from experimental instruments
- Wide variety of proprietary file formats but also preservation file formats
- Data often supports supplementary information in the associated manuscript
- Lots of code alongside data
- Researchers sometimes design software to use with the code
- Code often deposited on GitHub and linked to from the Apollo record

Why do physical scientists deposit the most?

- They generate the most data?
- They write more papers and deposit supporting data?
- More awareness of value of sharing data? Do they reuse data more?
- Fewer discipline specific repositories?
- Repository choice - what influences this?
- More sensitive data in other disciplines?
- How much data **isn't** being shared? Why? Where?

FAIR challenges for physical sciences

- Metadata/documentation sometimes neglected. Findable and Reusable challenge
- Institutional repositories often accept all research outputs and file formats. Interoperable challenge (for researchers and data curators).
- Proprietary file formats prevalent in physical sciences. Interoperable challenge
- Supplementary Information. Accessible/Findable challenge

How should researchers be educated and supported in good RDM and FAIR practices?

- Training e.g. [Research Skills Programme](#) at Cambridge
- Communities of Practice e.g. champions, stewards, data analytics, apprentices, technicians, dRTPs e.g. [CaSDaR](#) (Careers and Skills for data-driven Research)
- PSDI resources and networks
- Funders – RDM best practice, DMPs, policies
- Discipline specific tools and resources e.g. [PSDI](#) tools
- RDM services
- Conferences, events, workshops
- Publications or case studies – evidence-based research to show value of being FAIR

Summary

- Lots of challenges – but many researchers are (trying to) do the right thing
- We can support their disciplinary needs through tools, resources, training, and more generally
- RDM-interested communities essential to connect and reduce effort, raise awareness
- More research and evidence required to persuade researchers it is worthwhile being FAIR (so we can answer the ‘why’ questions)
- Involve researchers and learn from them

Contact

- Personal email cmc32@cam.ac.uk
- [Research Data website](#)
- Research Data Helpdesk info@data.cam.ac.uk
- [Data Champions website](#)
- [Chemistry Data Champions website](#) (may disappear soon!)

Questions?

Data curation in the life sciences

Chuck Cook

Program Manager

GLOBAL
BIODATA
COALITION

25 June 2025

PSDI Roadshow at Cambridge

Data sharing in the life sciences

- Life sciences: long history of open data sharing
- Archive primary life sciences research data
- Specialist repositories
- Added-value curation/analysis of primary data
- Thousands of resources
- Extensive collaboration and data exchange
- Highly interconnected
- A rich and interdependent ecosystem
- Used by all life science researchers

Data explosion in the life sciences

<https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkad1088>

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/about/statistics>

Many data types, many standards

- DNA/RNA/protein sequences
- Protein structures
- Expression arrays
- Small chemicals
- Macromolecular structures
- Ecology
- Biodiversity
- Literature
- Genomes
- Proteomes
- Molecular pathways
- Pathogen interactions
- Gene ontologies
- Protein, RNA families
- Metagenomes

Image reference: EMBL-EBI - www.ebi.ac.uk

Inventory of global biodata resources

- Discovery of biodata resources from the literature
- 3,773 biodata resources
- 58.5% of biodata resources name at least one of 2,265 funders
- Code configured into an executable pipeline with documentation in [GitHub](#) to facilitate reuse and future updates
- Publications
 - <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0294812>
 - https://zenodo.org/record/7767794#.ZGafrk_MLD5

Biodata resources: a global infrastructure

Crucial

- A healthy ecosystem of biodata resources underlies biological, life sciences & biomedical research across sectors

Distributed

- Highly distributed, scientist-led infrastructure that facilitates the efficient sharing of research data with usage crossing national, regional and continental borders

Open and connected

- High levels of openness with limited friction of access, supporting extensive data flows and links between biodata resources

Cost effective

- Spending to preserve research data is much lower than the cost of generating the data

Greater than the sum of its parts

- Value emerges typically from collections rather than individual data sets

Challenges for the biodata infrastructure

Demand increasing

- Increasing rate of data generation increases demand
- Open access policies increase demand
- Requirements for data management plans increase demand
- New technologies require new data resources or increase costs (AI)
- Staff shortages

<https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz959>

Sustainability challenges

Global Biodata Infrastructure

Image reference: Global Biodata Coalition - www.globalbiodata.org

- Funding has been haphazard, short term, and distributed unsystematically
- There is little global coordination among funders of these resources
- This global research infrastructure is not managed as an infrastructure
- The infrastructure is poorly described
- Vulnerable to funders' strategy and policy changes

Defining curation

- Research data
 - Researchers curate experimental data for archival submission
- Published literature
 - Curators extract data from the scientific literature, add to data resources
- Biodata resources curate submitted data
- Multiple data types

Archival repositories/ knowledgebases


```

RN [3]
RP 1-1102
RA Cook C.E.;
RT ;
RL Submitted (10-JUN-1993) to the INSDC.
RL Museum of Zoology, University of Cambridge, Downing St., Cambridge CB2 3EJ,
RL UK
XX
RN [4]
RC Sequence update by submitter
RP 1-1102
RA Cook C.E., Sensabaugh G.;
RT ;
RL Submitted (30-MAR-1999) to the INSDC.
RL Museum of Zoology, University of Cambridge, Downing St., Cambridge CB2 3EJ,
RL UK
XX
DR MD5; a098a011e5b623569e3a524b0e70e724.
XX
CC On Mar 30, 1999 this sequence version replaced gi:289784.
XX
FH Key Location/Qualifiers
FH
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FT /note="control region"
XX
SQ
Sequence 1102 BP; 360 A; 269 C; 148 G; 325 T; 0 other;
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ccagacctgc ttggagatcc agacaactat accccagcaa atccactcag cacaccccct 120
cacatcaaac cgaatgata cttcctattt gcatacgcaa tcctacgac aattcccac 180
aaactaggag gagtcttagc cctagctcca ctatcctaa tcttgattct catgcctttt 240
cttcacacgt ccaacaacg cagatgata ttccgacct tcagccaatg cctattctga 300
atcttagtag cagacctact aacctcaca tgaattggag gacaaccagt tgagtacct 360

```

Exchange of curated data

Data exchanges among ELIXIR Core Data Resources

<https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz959>

Data exchanges between EMBL-EBI and external data resources

<https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkz1033>

Openness and connectivity amplify the value of resources manyfold

Organizing a community

International Society for Biocuration

- Promotes biocuration
- Forum for biocurators
- Annual meetings
- Workshops
- Standards
- Promote stable funding
- Community building

Institutions: global cooperation

EMBL

国家生物信息中心

China National Center for Bioinformatics

Indian Biological
Data Centre

Swiss Institute of
Bioinformatics

National Library of Medicine

National Center for Biotechnology Information

- Think to the future
- Share the work
- Go global
- Plan for sustainability

Visit our website and:

- Read more about the GBC
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- Follow us on X and LinkedIn

PSDI

PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Data accessibility in the chemical sciences: an analysis of recent practice in organic chemistry journals

Exploring Data Curation in the Physical Sciences: PSDI Roadshow

25th June 2025

Dr Cerys Willoughby
University of Southampton

<https://www.psd.ac.uk/>

Impact of shared data on science

- ▶ Progressing science – building on the work of others
- ▶ Transparency – verification and validation
- ▶ Reproducibility
- ▶ Reusability
- ▶ Efficient use of resources
- ▶ Collaboration & innovation

Known issues within chemistry

Limited culture of data sharing:

- ▶ Difficult to find data that could be repurposed
- ▶ Difficult to validate and reproduce experiments
- ▶ Unnecessary duplication of experiments
- ▶ Limited examples of secondary analysis of open data
- ▶ Lack of data impedes the training of effective models
- ▶ Low yield results are not published resulting in a bias in the data
- ▶ Inhibits collaboration

Barriers to data sharing

- ▶ Unfamiliarity with data sharing concepts
- ▶ Not perceiving the benefits
- ▶ Poor data management training
- ▶ Lack of willingness to share
- ▶ Perceived lack of time for curation
- ▶ Lack of reward
- ▶ Many different file formats from a variety of tools and instruments
- ▶ Lack of adopted standards
- ▶ Not clear where the data should be shared
- ▶ Implementation costs
- ▶ Concerns around sensitive data

What is the state of play of data sharing practices in organic chemistry?

12 top journals

Using the FAIR Guiding Principles as a way of measuring accessibility of data

- ▶ Is there author compliance with recommended (but not compulsory) data policies?
- ▶ Do authors engage with recommendations for 'all data' deposition in open repositories, and are these data accessible and curated?
- ▶ Is there evidence to suggest that authors apply FAIR data guidance?
- ▶ Does the existence of specific recommendations for FAIR data practice in publishing NMR data by some journals encourage compliance?

Journal data policies (during study timeframe)

- ▶ All 12 journals *mandated* sharing of crystallographic data in CIF format
- ▶ 11 out of 12 journals *recommended* sharing 'all data' in a repository with some level of guidance on FAIR, but only *required* sharing in supplementary information (i.e. non-machine-readable format such as PDF or Word)
- ▶ 9 *recommended* deposition in a subject-specific repository but with little guidance
- ▶ 5 had additional guidance for NMR data
- ▶ None suggested a repository for NMR data

'All data' spectroscopic data (NMR, IR, UV-vis, Raman, circular dichroism and mass spectrometry), chromatography (GC, HPLC, SEC), physical data (m.p., b.p., elemental analysis, optical rotation), thermochemical data, computational data, structure information, cell culture and bioassay data; and excludes X-ray crystallography

PSDI
PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

FAIR variables

Looked at the data that was produced by the research in each article
Measured each paper and its associated data against 17 'FAIR' variables

FINDABILITY

The dataset is deposited in an open repository

The associated article is cited or linked

The dataset is assigned a unique, citable and persistent identifier (i.e., DOI)

All compounds are assigned a unique, citable and persistent identifier (i.e., SMILES or InChI + InChI key)

Data-time stamps for creation, deposition and versions of the dataset are included

Bibliographic metadata are available (authors, contributors, affiliations, funding source)

INTEROPERABILITY

Original data are in standard open format(s)

Metadata are in a machine-readable format (i.e., XML, JSON)

ACCESSIBILITY

Coherent file structure (logically grouped and labelled files)

README file describes the dataset

Unprocessed primary data are included

Metadata describe instrument parameters (vendor, model, version, software)

Metadata describe experiment parameters

Metadata describe data cleaning/analysis/processing/visualisation method(s)

REUSABILITY

Original data are in reusable format

Open licence information is available (i.e., CC or ODC) under which data can be reused

Code scripts necessary to reproduce findings are available

240
articles

Data produced by the research

- ▶ More than 95% of research articles report at least two types of data.

c) Number of articles with each data type²

- 239 of the 240 articles produced data
- Only 47 shared any primary data at all
- 39 of these shared 'MODEL' data derived from in silico modelling
- But 72% of those were in PDF files!
- 223 papers reported NMR data but only 3 provided primary data and none in *recommended* 'raw' FID format

Are data deposited in an open repository?

- ▶ Authors of only 4 articles uploaded data to a public repository of their own accord
- ▶ None used a subject-specific repository
- ▶ *Recommends* or even '*expecting*' that data is deposited in a repository does not encourage data sharing

a) SI and data files shared in a repository

b) Repository choices¹

Results look better than they are because the 4 ACS journals in the study automatically assign a DOI and upload to Figshare

Are all compounds assigned a
unique, citable and persistent
identifier?

No!
not even one

Despite widespread support in lab
software of SMILES, InChIs and
InChIKeys

Concerning loss of machine-readable
compound identifiers during the
publication process

Adherence to FAIR principles - Findable

47 studies that shared primary data – outputs assessed against the remaining FAIR variables

■ Yes ■ No

- ▶ Linking to the original article is distorted by ACS journals & Figshare
- ▶ Poor compliance because primary data in a PDF does not its own DOI
- ▶ None of the articles sharing primary data had timestamps for all elements.
- ▶ Bibliographic metadata relates closely to if the article is cited or linked

Adherence to FAIR principles - Accessible

- ▶ Sensible file naming and structure was seen only where the authors had packaged and shared their own data (6 articles)
- ▶ Only 2 articles provided a README to accompany the data
- ▶ About half the data files contained some metadata to describe instrument and experiment parameters (intrinsic to NMR data in JDX format) but other proprietary formats (MNOVA, SCN, MAE, MDP etc) do not enable access to all such metadata
- ▶ Although metadata about process could be derived manually from the PDF SI and linked articles, only 1 article provided this information directly with the data – where a Jupyter notebook with code was provided with the data

Adherence to FAIR principles - Interoperable

- ▶ Only 16 articles shared their data in native formats, 10 of which used open formats (PYNB, JDX, CSV, XYZ and TXT). Only JDX is a community accepted standard and CSV, XYZ, and TXT have challenges for interoperability because of a lack of standards
- ▶ Less than a third of shared data files have machine-readable metadata

Adherence to FAIR principles - Reusable

- ▶ Only 16 articles provided data in a native format that could be reused – but these were proprietary and would require specific software or conversion tools to use
- ▶ 27 publications had license information, but only 3 of these had license information associated with the data. Publisher led with ‘boilerplate’ licenses and ambiguity for data included in the PDF SI files. Where authors had uploaded their own data package to a repository, only 1 group set a license, and none had a license associated with the data
- ▶ Only one paper shared any code

Is there author compliance with recommended (but not compulsory) data policies?

a) Adheres to requirements

b) Exceeds requirements

- ▶ Compliance with *mandatory requirements* is excellent
- ▶ Compliance with *recommended policies* is poor
- ▶ Only 8 articles shared primary data that was not mandated
- ▶ Less than 20% of articles shared any primary data at all
- ▶ Only 16 articles shared data outside of the PDF/Word SI file
- ▶ Only 1 article shared any code that could enable verification or reuse

Do authors engage with recommendations for 'all data' deposition in open repositories and are these data accessible and curated?

No!

- ▶ Excluding the publisher-led deposition by ACS to Figshare, only 4 articles (<2%) deposited to a repository – none of which are subject-specific
- ▶ For these 4, reasonable curation and accessibility is in place, but not perfect

Is there evidence to suggest that authors apply FAIR data guidance in their data publishing practice?

No!

- ▶ Minimal primary data sharing, much of which is in tables in the PDF SI files
- ▶ 4 articles where data is intentionally shared, still missing key components
- ▶ Practice met FAIR guidance only superficially – e.g. 2 articles provided README but it lacked useful metadata or documentation.
- ▶ Only 16 shared primary data in native formats, only in a standard format
- ▶ None of the articles contained structure identifiers for compounds
- ▶ Metadata was poor, incomplete, and for most not in a machine-readable format
- ▶ Only one paper shared any code
- ▶ Sensible file naming and structure only where authors packaged and shared their own data
- ▶ Only 3 had had license information associated with the data

Does the existence of specific recommendations for FAIR data practice in the publishing of NMR data by some journals encourage compliance?

No!

- ▶ Of the 223 studies included here that produced NMR data, only 3 shared primary NMR data
- ▶ None in recommended FID format
- ▶ Only 1 in community adopted JDX format
- ▶ No acquisition and processing parameters were included
- ▶ None in an open repository for open NMR data

Why is compliance so poor?

- ▶ All the barriers mentioned before
- ▶ Journal *recommendations* only for data sharing
- ▶ Mandates are unpopular and researchers will publish elsewhere
- ▶ A lack of community adopted standards
- ▶ A lack of trusted open repositories
- ▶ A lack of discipline specific guidance
- ▶ Publish or perish – still a focus on the paper
- ▶ Manuscript submission platforms still push users towards PDF SI
- ▶ Reliance on researchers – could centralized facilities for NMR and MS data help?
- ▶ More education & tools needed

But... **crystallography** data doesn't have this problem

PSDI

PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Guidance for researchers

- ▶ Plan for data sharing up front – utilize Data Management Plans to reduce effort in curation
- ▶ Share primary data in a public repository with a DOI
- ▶ Use open file formats
- ▶ Document data and share metadata
- ▶ Include a README
- ▶ Include license information
- ▶ Include structure identifiers

Thanks for listening!

<https://doi.org/10.3762/bjoc.21.70>

UNIVERSITY OF
CAMBRIDGE

Cambridge
Data Champions

Overview of the Data Champion programme at Cambridge

Dr Kim Clugston, Research Data Coordinator

Office of Scholarly Communication
Cambridge University Library

About the Data Champion programme

Who are the Data Champions?

Cambridge's Data Champions are a community of volunteers from varied roles from across the University who are interested in research data management.

Why was it created?

To help support the University's community of c.10,000 researchers

What are the main goals?

- Improve research data management across the University
- Increase open research practices
- Improve research integrity
- Contribute to changing research culture

A timeline of the programme

Annual call for New Data Champions

Data Champions: Yearly Census

Data from December 2024 Data Champion Census

Data Champions across Schools

Data from December 2024 Data Champion Census

Data from December 2024 Data Champion Census across the 6 Schools

Data Champions hold a wide variety of roles ...

'Data professionals' bioinformatics training developer, data manager/scientist, clinical research data lead, senior study trial manager.

'Other' includes scientific officer, technical officer, grants administrator, project administrator, publishing manager, web developer, research assistant, research manager, project manager, research governance and information manager, research development and innovation manager, research facilitator, business analyst, research laboratory manager, projects coordinator, and more.

How the community works

- **Data Champions SharePoint/Microsoft Teams, email mailing list**
 - Share updates, training courses, webinars, troubleshooting.
- **Data Champion Forums (Bimonthly)**
 - Usually 12-2pm on Thursday
 - Lunch provided (funded by Cambridge University Press & Assessments)
 - Theme varies, the last few forums....Sensitive Data, Open Research, Collaborating internationally...etc
 - In-person and location varies throughout University
 - Speakers, networking, data troubleshooting
- **Workshops/webinars**
 - e.g. metadata, how to choose a repository, cyber security, research data sustainability, data storage infrastructure

What do Data Champions do?

Act as local points of contact

- Disseminating information
- Signposting to where to get help
- Training
- Identify discipline-specific RDM needs

Network

- Data Champion Forums
- Learn from experiences of other Data Champions

Advocate good research data management practice

- Department
- University wide
- Externally

Search for a Data Champion

- Data Champions can choose to have a web profile
- Visit: <https://www.data.cam.ac.uk/data-champions-search>
- Search to find a Data Champion by:
 - Expertise
 - Discipline

The screenshot displays the 'Data Champions Search' interface. It features a list of seven data champions, each with a profile picture, name, title, department, and a list of expertise areas. Below each profile are expandable sections for 'Contact Information' and 'Biography'. On the right side, there are search and filter options, including a search bar, 'Apply' and 'Reset' buttons, and checkboxes for filtering by area of expertise and research communities.

Data Champions Search

Jonathan Birchall, PhD
Research Associate
Department of Radiology
Areas Of Expertise: Git, Matlab, Data visualisation, Big data, Statistical analysis, Data collection, Data architecture, Version control, Experimental design, Data storage, Code sharing, Writing/publishing data papers, Surveys, Imaging, Textual data, Digital illustration
▶ Contact Information
▶ Biography

Shujing Shi
PhD student
Areas Of Expertise: R language, SQL, Data visualisation, Statistical analysis, Data collection, Sensitive data, Research data ethics, Surveys
▶ Contact Information
▶ Biography

Stefanie Felsberger
PhD student
Centre for Gender Studies, POLS
Areas Of Expertise: Data collection, Copyright, Sensitive data, Research data ethics, Data protection and research, Data policies, Data sharing, Open data, Writing/publishing data papers, Surveys, Workshop delivery
▶ Contact Information
▶ Biography

Abdulwahab Alshallal
PhD Student
Areas Of Expertise: Python, R language, Data visualisation, Big data, Statistical analysis, Research data ethics, Writing/publishing data papers
▶ Contact Information
▶ Biography

Aisha Sobey
Research Associate
Areas Of Expertise: Data Management Plans, Data collection, Sensitive data, Research data ethics, Surveys, Digitisation, Social media & digital communications
▶ Contact Information
▶ Biography

Alex Gushurst-Moore
Research & Impact Coordinator, Fitzwilliam Museum
Areas Of Expertise: Data visualisation, Data collection, Database design, Licensing, Copyright, Sensitive data, Research data ethics, Data protection and research, Data policies, Data storage, Institutional repositories, Open data, Digitisation, Social media & digital communications, Website development
▶ Contact Information
▶ Biography

Search / filter within these results
[Apply] [Reset]

Filter by area of expertise

- Specific techniques and software (64)
- Sharing and Storage (62)
- Data management (57)
- Data analysis (50)
- Coding (44)
- Training and Outreach skills (40)
- Ethics and the law (33)

Filter by research communities:

- Clinical Medicine (21)
- Biological Sciences (19)
- Humanities and Social Sciences (14)
- Non-School Institutions (12)
- Technology (6)
- Physical Sciences (5)
- Arts and Humanities (3)
- Affiliated Institutions (1)

UNIVERSITY OF
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Cambridge
Data Champions

If you are interested in becoming a Data Champion or to find out more:

Visit: <https://www.data.cam.ac.uk/intro-data-champions>

QR code:

Email: info@data.cam.ac.uk

**Powder diffraction data in scientific publications:
collecting data from the past and guidelines for the future**

Giulio Isacco Lampronti

gil21@cam.ac.uk

**X-Ray Facility, Department of
Materials Science & Metallurgy
University of Cambridge, UK**

xray.msm.cam.ac.uk
www.giuliolamprontibass.com

X-Rays @ MSM

xray.msm.cam.ac.uk

The screenshot shows the homepage of the MSM X-ray Facility website. The header is dark blue with the text "MSM X-ray Facility" in white. Below the header is a navigation menu with the following items: Home, About, Become a user (with a dropdown arrow), Equipment (with a dropdown arrow), Equipment Status, Software, Databases, Training Documents, and Staff & Contact. The main content area features a large blue-toned image of a mountain range. In the bottom left corner of this image, there is a dark blue box with the text "Welcome to the X-ray facility". On the right side of the page, there is a white box titled "Useful links" with the text "Click here for useful links to external sources such as databases and learning". A large QR code is overlaid on the bottom right of the page, enclosed in a green border.

Scientific Research facility: PXRD, thin film analysis, SAXS instruments.
Training, assistance, consultancy, on single crystal, powder, thin film data
collection and analysis

FAIR data – some pragmatic questions

FAIR principles

data should be:

Findable

Accessible

Interoperable

Reusable

FAIR data – some pragmatic questions

FAIR principles
data should be:
Findable
Accessible
Interoperable
Reusable

Financial
sustainability?

FAIR data – some pragmatic questions

FAIR data – some pragmatic questions

**High res images and videos: largest fraction of data on servers
(source: Statista, "Big Data" report)**

The Power Of Powders

Figure 1 General information content of a powder diffraction pattern.

Dinnebier, Robert E., and Simon JL Billinge, eds. Powder diffraction: theory and practice. Royal society of chemistry, 2008.

The Power Of Powders

PXRD is

- **profoundly insightful**
- **versatile and flexible**
easy and quick to perform
can operate in-situ as f(T, P, B, X, etc)
- **data-efficient**
typical 1-D scan <<1Mb

The Power Of Powders

PXRD is

- **profoundly insightful**
- **versatile and flexible**
easy and quick to perform
can operate in-situ (T, P, B, X, etc)
- **data-efficient**
typical 1-D scan <<1Mb

Databases: past data mining

Experimental powder diffraction data and associated information (composition, crystal structure, physical properties) from the scientific literature:

wide ranging, spotty, inconsistent

On the Structure of Bismuthsesquioxide: the α , β , γ , and δ -Phase

By H. A. HARWIG

Utrecht (The Netherlands), Inorganic Chemistry Department, State University

Abstract. The structures of four polymorphs of Bi_2O_3 were investigated by means of X-ray and neutron powder diffraction. The position parameters of the oxygen atoms in $\alpha\text{-Bi}_2\text{O}_3$ were refined. High temperature neutron diffraction shows that a complicated disorder exists in the oxygen sublattice of the fluorite related structure of the solid electrolyte $\delta\text{-Bi}_2\text{O}_3$. X-ray diffraction data on metastable $\beta\text{-Bi}_2\text{O}_3$ correspond with a distorted fluorites structure with the voids in the oxygen sublattice ordered in the $\langle 001 \rangle$ direction. X-ray and neutron diffraction data indicate that metastable $\gamma\text{-Bi}_2\text{O}_3$ is isomorphous to $\text{Bi}_{12}\text{GeO}_{20}$.

Fig. 2: Neutron diffraction profile of $\alpha\text{-Bi}_2\text{O}_3$ at room temperature

Databases: past data mining

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Fig. 2: Neutron diffraction profile of α - Bi_2O_3 at room temperature

AI toolsets for data retrieval from scientific publications are currently being developed.

(e.g.: Berry, Joshua, and Katerina A. Christofidou. "Supervised machine learning for multi-principal element alloy structural design." *Materials Science and Technology* (2024): 02670836241272086.

Databases: guidelines for the future

How do we make Experimental powder diffraction data and associated information in the scientific publications **more consistent and complete?**

powder diffraction data in FAIR format (CIF)

CIF also contains sample and data collection metadata

associated materials properties?

associated diffraction standard collections

failed experiments and relative information

xray.msm.cam.ac.uk

MSM X-ray Facility

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THANK YOU

Welcome to the X-ray facility

Useful links

Click here for useful links to external sources such as databases and learning

Scientific Research facility: PXRD, thin film analysis, SAXS instruments.
Training, assistance, consultancy, on single crystal, powder, thin film data
collection and analysis

GigaDB data curation (biological data)

Chris Hunter

Exploring Data Curation and Management in Physical Sciences: PSDI Roadshow Cambridge,
25th June 2025

GigaScience Press

- GigaScience Press (GSPress) is an academic publisher currently publishing the *GigaScience* and *GigaByte* journals. Both in the Life Sciences domain.

For more information about these journals please visit the websites:

<http://gigasciencejournal.com/>

<https://gigabytejournal.com/>

- The unique feature of GSPress is our in-house data-curation and data-publishing team under the moniker “GigaDB”.

<https://gigadb.org>

- GSPress is fully Open Access, both journals and the database

Transparency & Reproducibility

- One key principle of all GSPress journals is **transparency**, a major component of which is reproducibility.
- There are 4 aspects to the reproducibility of research as shown in the matrix below;

	Same Data	Different Data
Same Method	Reproducibility	Replicability
Different Method	Robustness	Generalisability

- Highlighted top left is the reason why we have GigaDB

(GIGA)ⁿDB

GigaDB

- Try to ensure Transparency and reproducibility of published articles
- Provide a home for data that does not have a community repository.
- Curate links to all data objects from our datasets
- We distinguish between “data”- in a data repository, and “supplemental information”- as pdf or similar with the journal article.
- Data Inspection – to ensure all underlying data is openly available
- We follow the FAIR Principals (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)

Manuscript Submission Pipeline

(GIGA)ⁿ DB

Thanks for listening

Chris Hunter – GigaDB Director

Mary Ann Tuli – Senior Data Editor

Yannan Fan – Assistant Data Editor

Bastien Molcrette - Data Editor

Working With Authors Prior to Publication to Ensure Life Science Data Meets GigaScience Press' Standards

(GIGA)ⁿ DB

- ❖ Data Inspection - work with authors and editors
- ❖ FAIR Principals of Open Access
 - ❖ Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

Data Inspection

Subject-specific Repositories

Biological Databases	Software	Other
INSDC (EBI, NCBI, DDBJ) - Sequence Data Archive	GitHub - Software Projects	Protocols.io – Protocol Management
ArrayExpress – Functional Genomics	GitLab – Code Management	SciCrunch – Resources Database
ProteomeXchange - Proteomics	WorkflowHub – Computational Workflows	SketchFab - 3D models
MetabolomeXchange - Metabolomics	Docker - Containers	Thingiverse – 3D models
GEO – Gene Expression	Singularity - Containers	FigShare – Broad scope
EGA - genetic and phenotypic data (secure)	Code Ocean - Computational Reproducibility	Zenodo – Broad scope
UKBiobank – biomedical data (secure)	Software Heritage Library – Archived Code	Dryad – Broad scope
	Galaxy – Analysis of Large Datasets	ScienceDB – Broad scope
		DOME-ML – Machine Learning

Published

JOURNAL ARTICLE

Genomic evidence for hybridization and introgression between blue peafowl and endangered green peafowl and molecular foundation of leucistic plumage of blue peafowl

Gang Wang, Xinye Zhang, Xiurong Zhao, Xufang Ren, Anqi Chen, Wenting Dai, Li Zhang, Yan Lu, Zhihua Jiang, Huie Wang ... Show more

GigaScience, Volume 14, 2025, giae124, <https://doi.org/10.1093/gigascience/giae124>

Published: 19 February 2025 Article history

Data Availability

The datasets presented in this study can be found in online repositories. The genome assembly and corresponding sequencing data were deposited in NCBI with BioProject accession number PRJNA1143721 and CNGBdb with accession number CNP0004612. The whole sequencing data and green peafowl Hi-C data collected were from BioProject accession numbers CNP0002498, PRJNA665082, PRJNA340135, and PRJNA644939. RNA sequencing data collected were from BioProject accession numbers PRJNA661158 and PRJNA271731. The codes for reproducing the results are also provided in the GitHub repository [159]. All additional supporting data are available in the GigaScience repository, GigaDB [160].

(GIGA)ⁿ DB
Revolutionizing data dissemination, organization, and use

Home About Help Terms of use

Supporting data for "Genomic evidence for hybridization and introgression between blue peafowl and endangered green peafowl and molecular foundation of peafowl white plumage"

Dataset type: Genomic, Metagenomic
Data released on December 23, 2024

DOI: [10.5524/102625](https://doi.org/10.5524/102625) Cite Dataset

Accessions (data included in GigaDB):
BioProject: [PRJNA1143721](#)

Accessions (data not in GigaDB):
CNSA_project: [CNP0002498](#)
BioProject: [PRJNA665082](#)
BioProject: [PRJNA340135](#)
BioProject: [PRJNA644939](#)
BioProject: [PRJNA661158](#)

Sample Files Funding History

Click on a table column to sort the results. Table Settings

File Name	Description	Data Type	Size	File Attributes	Download
Raw-data_meta_informati on.tsv	The list of DNA raw data and re-used data meta information including, BioProject ID, BioSample ID, sequencing method, phenotype (species), and whether generated from this study	Tabular data	4.09 kB	MD5 checksum: 2e05f2cea1473f2f495bfefd45a26338	Download
readme_102625.txt		Readme	27.57 kB	MD5 checksum: a0451d2b4e531025833079f4e8176c69	Download
RNA-Raw-data_meta_informati on.tsv	The list of RNA raw data and re-used data meta information including, BioProject ID, BioSample ID, sequencing method, phenotype (species), and whether generated from this study	Tabular data	2.69 kB	MD5 checksum: f7fffacb382c180d97f20e4c791f1f154	Download
Sample.information.t xt	The list of sample metadata information including, BioProject ID, BioSample ID, sequencing method, phenotype (species), and whether generated from this study	Tabular data	9.27 kB	MD5 checksum: 9c1752da8727574e576ff51c8dcb8b4b	Download
short_summary.specif ic.aves_odb10.White _Pavo.txt	The BUSCO result (v5.3+) for the genome which is underlying data for Table 1 in the associated manuscript	BUSCO	707 B	MD5 checksum: ab14411ba99c688e1bdca0239258911 Table in MS: 1	Download

Summary

- Prior to peer review
- Higher quality submissions
- Educates authors on best practices
- Better for reviewers

(GIGA)ⁿ DB

Chris Hunter – GigaDB Director

Mary Ann Tuli – Senior Data Editor

Yannan Fan – Assistant Data Editor

Bastien Molcrette - Data Editor

BioFAIR in five minutes:

Driving Culture Change in Research Data Management in the UK Life Sciences

Nishadi De Silva

Senior Technical Project Manager, BioFAIR

PSDI roadshow, Cambridge - Wednesday 25th June 2025

BioFAIR

What is BioFAIR?

BioFAIR is a new federated digital research infrastructure that will deliver a step change in 'Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable' (FAIR) research data management (RDM), providing end-to-end FAIR RDM & analysis capabilities along with the necessary support and training for UK researchers working in the life sciences.

BioFAIR is a five year, £34m UK-government funded initiative, co-led by the Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC) and Medical Research Council (MRC), on behalf of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

Digital Research Infrastructure...?

Data Repositories

Versioning and lineage tracking are crucial. They ensure data integrity and reproducibility.

Compute Engines

HPC clusters and cloud bursts provide computational power. Access providing by platforms e.g. AnVIL, DNAnexus

Workflow Orchestration

Galaxy, Nextflow, and Snakemake manage pipelines. They automate complex research workflows.

Interoperability & APIs

Standard metadata, formats, and APIs are essential. BAM, VCF, JSON, AnnData are common examples.

User Support

Documentation, workshops, and helpdesks assist researchers to make effective use of the infrastructure.

Our Objectives

Culture change

To drive adoption of FAIR principles and open data across the UK life sciences to provide high quality FAIR datasets ready for uptake and reuse.

Defragmentation

To increase the coordination, collaboration and cohesiveness of the UK's life science related data landscape, enhancing its effectiveness and efficiency.

Access

To enable democratised access to data and data methods within UK life sciences via a national capability.

Skills

To attract, develop and retain excellent research data management skills and capacity for UK life sciences.

Data reuse

To improve the efficiency of research and enabling new research by increased re-use of data in the life sciences.

Our BioCommons

Data

Enabling researchers to prepare, analyse, share and manage FAIR research data across the data's whole life cycle

Method

Enabling institutes and research teams to access trusted and robust analysis platforms, workflows and tools, using their own and reference datasets

People

A pooled community of data software stewards and Research Software Engineers supporting Data and Software Management Planning

Get Involved!

Newsletter - Sign up at www.biofair.uk

Socials - @BioFAIRUK

Fellowship Opportunities - Launched last week!

Pathfinder projects up next - share your ideas

Contact us

info@biofair.uk

www.biofair.uk

PSDI

PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Data Management Plans for the Physical Sciences

Exploring Data Curation in the Physical Sciences: PSDI Roadshow

25th June 2025

Dr Cerys Willoughby & Dr Louise Saul

University of Southampton

<https://www.psdia.ac.uk/>

Benefits of Data Management Plans

- ▶ Improving data management
- ▶ Ensuring proper storage and protection of the data
- ▶ Considering long-term preservation and curation
- ▶ Making it easier to share the data
- ▶ Enhancing reproducibility by documenting the processes and provenance of the data
- ▶ Compliance with funder and institutional requirements
- ▶ Supporting ethical and legal considerations
- ▶ Metadata could be reused

Barriers for Data Management Plans

- ▶ Time and effort
- ▶ Reliance on filling in lots of boxes with text
- ▶ Lack of subject-specific examples for physical sciences
- ▶ Guidance is generic or lacks relevancy to physical sciences data
- ▶ Seen as a box-ticking exercise
- ▶ Not perceived as a useful living document

A Data Management Plan for Physical Sciences

- ▶ Examples of good practice shared by the community? ✘
- ▶ Examples of good practice from School of Chemistry at Southampton? ✘
- ▶ Problems: Not much out there, very specific and difficult to anonymise, few examples of 'good practice'
- ▶ NFDI4Chem work: results from RDA WG Discipline-specific Guidance for DMP online survey, NFDI4Chem Survey & Interviews; developed a DMP
- ▶ Updated for a UK audience
- ▶ Followed DCC Guidance on what should be in a DMP

A Data Management Plan for PSDI

The screenshot shows a web browser displaying the PSDI Knowledge Base page for 'Data Management Plan for the Physical Sciences'. The page has a navigation menu on the left with categories like 'Getting started with PSDI', 'Guidance', 'Research Data Management', 'Data Management Planning', and 'DMP for Physical Sciences'. The main content area features a title 'Data Management Plan for the Physical Sciences' and an introductory paragraph. Below this is an 'INFO' box with text about the DMP's development and a link to an example. The page is divided into sections: 'About this Data Management Plan', 'What is the ID of this data management plan?', 'Who owns this data management plan?', and 'What updates have been made to this data management plan?'. Each section includes a 'Guidance' paragraph and a form field. A right-hand sidebar contains a list of questions related to the DMP, such as 'What is the ID of this data management plan?' and 'Who owns this data management plan?'. The browser's address bar shows the URL: guidance.psd1.ac.uk/docusaurus-pages/docs/guidance/data-management/data-management-planning/dmps/psdi-dmp.

We need feedback from the community!

- ▶ It's very long!
- ▶ It needs to be in an alternative format:
 - ▶ form
 - ▶ Word
 - ▶ Excel
 - ▶ ??
- ▶ Option to hide guidance?
- ▶ More completed examples from different disciplines

A few questions from you

We'll give you 10 minutes to look at the DMP and then ask you the following questions: <https://tinyurl.com/psdi-dmp>

- ▶ Is there a need for a physical sciences DMP?
- ▶ Would it be helpful for us to provide the DMP in a form format, with dropdowns and radio buttons for example?
- ▶ Which sections are the most important?
- ▶ What have we missed from this DMP – is there anything that would improve it?
- ▶ Do you have an idea for a better tool to capture this information?

Please note down any thoughts as you go through, and we are grateful for more in-depth feedback after the session if anyone would like to provide it

VEVOX SESSION

- ▶ Go to vevox.com
- ▶ Enter the session ID: 194-668-815

Is there a need for a physical
sciences DMP?

Would it be helpful for us to provide the DMP in a form format, with dropdowns and radio buttons for example?

Which sections are the most important?

What have we missed from
this DMP – is there anything
that would improve it?

Do you have an idea for a
better tool to capture this
information?

**Thank you for
contributing!**

Streamlining Data Curation:

Lessons from Crystallography

Ian Bruno

Director of Data Initiatives

PSDI Roadshow @ Cambridge, 25 June 2025

CCDC
advancing structural science

Early Publication of Crystal Structure Data

Acta Cryst. (1948). 1, 324

The Structures of Pyrimidines and Purines. II. A Determination of the Structure of Adenine Hydrochloride by X-ray Methods

BY JUNE M. BROOMHEAD

Crystallographic Laboratory, Cavendish Laboratory, University of Cambridge, England

(Received 24 August 1948 and in revised form 8 October 1948)

Table 2. Comparison of observed and calculated structure amplitudes

AMI	F _{obs}	F _{calc}	AMI	F _{obs}	F _{calc}	AMI	F _{obs}	F _{calc}
002	10	14	10,10	8	9	704	0	3
004	10	14	10,12	9	8	702	11	-9
008	11	15	10,14	8	6	708	7	4
012	5	3	10,16	6	6	706	8	-10
016	5	3	10,18	0	0	704	0	2
020	6	0	10,20	0	0	706	0	-6
024	12	11	10,24	4	4	706	6	6
028	9	5	10,28	3	4	702	0	0
032	4	3	10,32	10	10	702	3	-2
100	2	0	408	5	6	702	3	-2
104	4	3	408	10	10	702	3	-2
108	11	11	408	7	6	702	3	-2
112	10	10	408	8	8	702	3	-2
116	19	18	408	6	6	702	3	-2
120	3	2	408	8	8	702	3	-2
124	7	15	408	10	10	702	3	-2
128	11	15	408	6	7	702	3	-2
132	5	6	408	18	21	702	3	-2
136	9	9	408	8	8	702	3	-2
140	0	0	408	4	4	702	3	-2
144	18	21	408	6	6	702	3	-2
148	18	21	408	8	8	702	3	-2
152	18	21	408	11	11	702	3	-2
156	18	21	408	8	8	702	3	-2
160	18	21	408	11	11	702	3	-2
164	18	21	408	4	4	702	3	-2
168	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
172	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
176	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
180	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
184	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
188	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
192	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
196	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
200	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
204	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
208	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
212	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
216	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
220	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
224	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
228	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
232	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
236	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
240	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
244	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
248	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
252	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
256	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
260	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
264	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
268	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
272	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
276	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
280	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
284	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
288	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
292	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
296	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2
300	18	21	408	3	4	702	3	-2

Table 1. Atomic co-ordinates expressed as fractions of the corresponding unit-cell dimension

$a = 8.771, b = 4.834, c = 19.46 \text{ \AA}, \beta = 114^\circ 15'$

Atom	x	y	z
H ₂ O	0	0.745	0
Cl	0.2817	0.178	0.0257
N ₁	0.8200	0.407	0.3450
N ₂	0.6033	0.246	0.2358
N ₃	0.8033	0.788	0.1833
N ₉	0.5967	0.504	0.1300
N ₁₀	0.0992	0.767	0.3550
C ₂	0.6929	0.237	0.3105
C ₄	0.6550	0.443	0.2000
C ₅	0.7933	0.630	0.2368
C ₆	0.8783	0.005	0.3142
C ₈	0.6883	0.716	0.1200

Description of the structure
Bond distances within the molecule and interbond angles are given in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Bond lengths and bond angles.

NATURE No. 4102 June 12, 1948 Crystal Structure of Polyvinyl Alcohol

Electron track records in radioactive decay, N_2^{15} molecules were studied in dilute thorium and uranium nitrate solutions, and electron tracks were recorded at the origin of alpha-tracks. Figs. 1 and 2 show photographs of alpha-tracks of thorium X with beta-tracks probably due to the decay of thorium X₂. The beta-ray energy (Fig. 1) should, according to the table, correspond roughly to 25 kV. Fig. 3 represents an alpha-track due to thorium C, and the beta-particle is due to the parent element thorium B, which has been ejected before the alpha-emission. A second beta-particle is believed to be seen as being ejected from the same origin. This may be attributed to the beta-emission from thorium C'. Fig. 3 is a photograph-remnant of a plane-projection of a three-dimensional radiothorium star at the origin of which an electron track is seen. The second electron track visible in this photograph may be the end of a track of an electron of higher energy arising from the same origin.

Alger mode. While scanning the electron tracks it was observed that some tracks show clumping of grains at the beginning and at the end of tracks (see above in Fig. 4). This phenomenon can probably be attributed to the Alger effect. Although the specific ionization is greater at the end of the tracks, in some cases branching of short secondary tracks will be recorded in the emulsion by heavier ionizations at the beginning of the tracks.

I am indebted to Messrs. E. H. Kennedy and G. F. Cooke for their assistance in this work.

R. H. HESS
Research Laboratories, Kodak, Ltd.,
Weybridge, Middlesex,
Engl.

* *Bosman, R. W., J. Chem. Phys.* 16, 422 (1948).
* *Waller, H., Ann. Phys.* 16, 218 (1955); 186, 107 (1955).
* *Waller, H., Ann. Phys.* 16, 219 (1955).
* *Waller, H., J. Polym. Sci. Polym. Chem. Ed.* 1, 100, 100 (1963).

Crystal Structure of Polyvinyl Alcohol

It has often been said (by me as well as by others) that the molecular repeat distance (from X-ray diffraction photographs) of polyvinyl alcohol—2.82 Å—indicates not only that the chain has a simple phase zigzag configuration, but also that all the hydroxyl groups (in the section of a molecule in one crystallite) lie on the same side of the zigzag plane. This is not necessarily true; in fact as X-ray diffraction is concerned, the observed repeat distance is equally compatible with a molecular structure in which hydroxyl groups are randomly placed in left- and right-hand positions. This possibility was not considered until recently; it was assumed that the high degree of crystallinity of polyvinyl alcohol implied regularity of molecular structure. Recently, however, it has been found that interlayers of ethylene and vinyl alcohol are crystalline; thus hydroxyl groups may replace hydroxyl atoms at random on a carbon chain without destroying crystallinity; the high crystallinity of polyvinyl alcohol

cannot, therefore, be regarded as evidence against the idea of amorphous irregularity in this molecule.

To determine whether the hydroxyl groups are randomly or regularly placed, the interpretation of X-ray diffraction patterns of polyvinyl alcohol films has been considered in detail. In agreement with Moseley's, a two-molecule monosyllabic unit cell is found to account for the positions of X-ray reflections; this cell has $a = 7.41 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 2.52 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 5.51 \text{ \AA}$, $\beta = 91^\circ 42'$; these figures agree fairly well with those of Moseley, who, however, gives $\beta = 90^\circ$. No structure embodying regular molecules gave correct relative intensities for the X-ray reflections; all possible arrangements (including that proposed by Moseley) and all possible molecular parameters were considered. But a particular arrangement of molecules with hydroxyl groups randomly placed in left- and right-hand positions accounts in a highly satisfactory way for the entire X-ray diffraction pattern; calculated intensities agree very well with those observed. This arrangement has the symmetry $P2_1/m$ with C (of CH₂) at 0.190 a, 0.250 b, 0.806 c, C (of CH) at 0.277 a, 0.750 b, 0.708 c, half the oxygen atoms at 0.451 a, 0.750 b, 0.782 c, and the other half at 0.267 a, 0.750 b, 0.450 c. The arrangement, which is illustrated in the accompanying projections, may be described as a layer structure; a double layer of molecules is held together by hydroxyl bonds; between one double layer and the next the

Publication of data including structure factors required by IUCr since 1948

Collective Data: Origins

- Funding from the Royal Society in 1965 to assemble a **computer-based file of bibliographic information and numerical data**
- Data first published in printed volumes generated from the file

Bibliography 1935-69 General Organic Crystal Structures

Edited by Olga Kennard and David G. Watson

Published for the
Crystallographic Data Centre Cambridge
and the
International Union of Crystallography
by N.V. A.Oosthoek's Uitgevers Mij Utrecht

Early Search

Succinyl hydrazide	8	33	7
Succinylcholine iodide	7	1	35
Succinylcholine iodide	3	3	51
Succinylcholine perchlorate	4	1	13
Succinylcholine picrate	7	3	31
Succinyl diamide	1	1	133
Succinylsuccinate	7	21	2
Sucrose	7	45	37
Sucrose	5	45	31
Sucrose	5	45	29
Sucrose	5	45	28
Sucrose	5	45	30n
Sucrose	6	45	35
Sucrose	1	45	69n
Sucrose-sodium bromide dihydrate	1	45	70
Sulfadiazine	8	44	19
Sulfadiazine	8	44	17
Sulfadimethoxine	8	44	21
Sulfaguanidine monohydrate	8	16	3
Sulfaguanidine monohydrate	8	16	4
Sulfamoyl-benzo-1,2,4-thiadiazine 1,1-dioxide	5	41	10
Sulfamoyl-1,2,4-benzothiadiazine 1,1-dioxide	5	41	13
Sulfamoylanthranilic acid	8	38	24
Sulfane-1,6-diyl)-1,2-hydrazinedicarboxylate	7	4	5
Sulfanilamide	4	16	3
Sulfanilamide	1	16	21n
Sulfanilamide	1	16	19
Sulfanilamide	1	16	18
Sulfanilamide	1	16	17
Sulfanilamide	1	16	20
Sulfanilamide	5	16	3
Sulfanilamide	3	41	7
Sulfanilamide	4	41	10
Sulfanilamide	4	41	9
Sulfanilamide	5	11	5
Sulfanilamide - sulfathiazole complex	3	60	30
Sulfanilamide complex	1	16	22
Sulfanilamide monohydrate	1	16	14
Sulfanilamide monohydrate	8	44	17
Sulfanilamide	8	44	19
Sulfanilamide)	4	66	8
Sulfanilamido-pyrimidine	7	16	2
Sulfanilamido-6-methoxy-pyridazine) bismuth(III)	7	16	2

CARBOHYDRATES

45.23 Ramucoside monohydrate
C₁₁H₁₈O₈ · H₂O C.P. Rasmussen *Acta Cryst. (B)*, **29**, 1030, 1973

45.28 **Sucrose (low angle data only)**
C₁₂H₂₂O₁₁
J.C.Hanson, L.C.Sieker, L.H.Jensen *Acta Cryst. (B)*, **29**, 797, 1973

45.29 **Sucrose (high angle data only)**
C₁₂H₂₂O₁₁
J.C.Hanson, L.C.Sieker, L.H.Jensen *Acta Cryst. (B)*, **29**, 797, 1973

45.30 **Sucrose (neutron study, refinement)**
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G.M.Brown, H.A.Levy *Acta Cryst. (B)*, **29**, 790, 1973

W.J.Cook, C.E.Bugg
Amer. Cryst. Assoc. Abstr. Papers (Winter Meeting), 58, 1973
Residue 1 also classified in 67

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45.30 Sucrose (neutron study, refinement)
C₁₂H₂₂O₁₁
G.M.Brown, H.A.Levy *Acta Cryst. (B)*, **29**, 790, 1973

45.39 α-Trehalose calcium bromide dihydrate
C₁₂H₂₂O₁₂ · Ca²⁺ · 2Br⁻ · 2H₂O
W.J.Cook, C.E.Bugg
Amer. Cryst. Assoc. Abstr. Papers (Winter Meeting), 58, 1973
Residue 1 also classified in 67

45.40 1,2,3,4-Tetra-O-acetyl-α-D-arabinopyranoside
C₁₃H₁₈O₉
V.James *Stockholm Symposium*, 100, 1973

45.41 1,2,3,4-Tetra-O-acetyl-β-D-arabinopyranoside
C₁₃H₁₈O₉
V.James *Stockholm Symposium*, 100, 1973

Early Database Creation

Hand-typed tables of coordinates in journal articles manually transcribed into database records

Table 4. Structure factors
See text for explanation

Table 3. Coordinates and thermal parameters, with standard errors, for the crystal structure of sucrose, all times 10⁵
The anisotropic temperature factor has the form $\exp(-\beta_{11}h^2 - \beta_{22}k^2 - \beta_{33}l^2 - 2\beta_{12}hk - 2\beta_{13}hl - 2\beta_{23}kl)$.

ATOM	X	Y	Z	β_{11}	β_{22}	β_{33}	β_{12}	β_{13}	β_{23}
C (1)	23961 (8)	35792 (0)	48487 (12)	274 (6)	376 (9)	584 (12)	6 (6)	94 (7)	4 (3)
C (2)	31253 (9)	47074 (15)	63800 (12)	304 (6)	489 (10)	641 (13)	-44 (7)	73 (7)	-6 (3)
C (3)	28545 (9)	63673 (15)	56447 (13)	321 (7)	437 (10)	965 (15)	-18 (7)	196 (8)	-72 (10)
C (4)	37494 (10)	67095 (15)	44198 (14)	400 (7)	403 (10)	1003 (15)	-22 (7)	243 (9)	6 (11)
C (5)	35925 (9)	55107 (16)	29529 (13)	314 (7)	525 (11)	756 (14)	-23 (7)	133 (8)	64 (10)
C (6)	45754 (11)	57083 (17)	18455 (14)	525 (8)	749 (14)	858 (15)	-133 (9)	307 (9)	-2 (12)
C* (1)	10301 (10)	13110 (15)	54380 (12)	463 (8)	559 (11)	517 (12)	-71 (8)	152 (8)	104 (9)
C* (2)	12446 (8)	19262 (14)	36895 (10)	307 (6)	362 (9)	426 (11)	-6 (6)	101 (6)	32 (8)
C* (3)	718 (8)	19075 (15)	21485 (11)	288 (6)	430 (9)	521 (11)	-32 (6)	106 (7)	19 (9)
C* (4)	6478 (9)	16653 (15)	5476 (13)	354 (6)	474 (10)	464 (11)	-39 (7)	107 (7)	-2 (9)
C* (5)	17635 (9)	6133 (15)	12864 (12)	393 (7)	440 (10)	565 (12)	27 (7)	152 (7)	-62 (9)
C* (6)	28927 (10)	8194 (17)	4668 (14)	482 (8)	795 (14)	814 (15)	81 (9)	303 (9)	-49 (12)
O (1)	17143 (9)	34630 (15)	39165 (13)	272 (7)	340 (10)	611 (13)	-5 (7)	86 (8)	18 (10)
O (2)	22954 (12)	43550 (19)	74766 (16)	488 (10)	749 (15)	668 (16)	-67 (10)	206 (10)	-40 (13)
O (3)	30801 (13)	74770 (19)	70279 (21)	577 (12)	656 (16)	1650 (27)	-213 (11)	607 (15)	-516 (17)
O (4)	34880 (18)	81412 (20)	35631 (24)	1042 (17)	478 (15)	1629 (29)	151 (13)	593 (19)	271 (18)
O (5)	37719 (10)	39878 (16)	36884 (15)	316 (8)	442 (12)	837 (16)	-1 (8)	224 (9)	-20 (11)
O (6)	58144 (13)	54525 (21)	28621 (20)	384 (9)	878 (19)	1425 (24)	-118 (11)	379 (12)	-199 (17)
O* (1)	3017 (12)	23548 (20)	62119 (16)	503 (9)	859 (16)	690 (16)	-75 (11)	314 (10)	-26 (13)
O* (2)	21205 (10)	9445 (16)	31572 (13)	400 (8)	472 (12)	540 (13)	124 (8)	78 (8)	-17 (10)
O* (3)	-7367 (11)	31776 (17)	20452 (16)	337 (8)	602 (13)	856 (17)	109 (9)	126 (10)	64 (13)
O* (4)	-2123 (12)	9734 (19)	-8904 (14)	502 (10)	836 (16)	541 (15)	-143 (10)	39 (10)	-62 (12)
O* (6)	32644 (13)	23799 (21)	4035 (17)	553 (11)	931 (18)	852 (19)	-125 (12)	259 (11)	36 (15)
H (C1)	33468 (20)	24508 (27)	53886 (29)	509 (16)	610 (22)	1155 (33)	74 (16)	112 (18)	159 (22)
H (C2)	41158 (21)	4693 (33)	71166 (31)	440 (16)	1125 (32)	1123 (36)	-21 (19)	-65 (19)	-86 (28)
H (C3)	18707 (20)	64476 (32)	48969 (34)	412 (15)	947 (30)	1749 (44)	59 (18)	146 (21)	46 (30)
H (C4)	47171 (21)	66808 (34)	52180 (33)	502 (17)	1118 (33)	1462 (39)	-193 (20)	228 (20)	-153 (31)
H (C5)	26384 (21)	56129 (35)	20931 (32)	492 (16)	1135 (34)	1347 (38)	11 (21)	-29 (20)	149 (30)
H (C6)	45305 (32)	68728 (40)	13445 (42)	1101 (31)	1212 (41)	1993 (58)	-11 (31)	607 (35)	652 (42)
H* (C6)	43723 (32)	99265 (46)	7189 (39)	1023 (30)	1939 (37)	1272 (43)	-462 (35)	454 (29)	-556 (40)
H* (C* 1)	5199 (30)	2238 (32)	52157 (36)	1129 (30)	800 (30)	1425 (43)	-345 (25)	436 (30)	-60 (29)
H* (C* 1)	19473 (24)	10908 (36)	63300 (31)	732 (20)	1337 (38)	975 (32)	145 (24)	102 (21)	369 (30)
H (C* 3)	-4946 (21)	8843 (27)	22896 (28)	556 (17)	728 (25)	1116 (32)	-181 (17)	212 (19)	25 (23)
H (C* 4)	9840 (22)	27720 (27)	1551 (29)	635 (18)	787 (25)	1101 (33)	-58 (18)	273 (20)	231 (24)
H (C* 5)	14653 (25)	-5988 (29)	11325 (32)	846 (22)	610 (23)	1204 (35)	-74 (19)	270 (24)	-154 (23)
H (C* 6)	36724 (30)	1189 (42)	11947 (48)	743 (24)	1541 (49)	2281 (66)	462 (29)	466 (33)	491 (46)
H* (C* 6)	26505 (31)	3991 (41)	-8870 (36)	1114 (29)	1451 (43)	1227 (39)	-116 (32)	580 (29)	-464 (36)
H (O2)	27193 (26)	37235 (36)	84664 (31)	845 (23)	1253 (37)	969 (34)	-77 (26)	172 (33)	185 (31)
H (O3)	23175 (29)	76597 (36)	74255 (44)	888 (27)	1047 (34)	2332 (60)	-253 (25)	832 (34)	-598 (38)
H (O4)	34066 (58)	89130 (40)	43250 (60)	3073 (88)	695 (35)	2880 (91)	367 (47)	1812 (78)	149 (47)
H (O6)	60152 (31)	43834 (39)	28663 (46)	890 (28)	1052 (39)	2121 (62)	26 (27)	340 (33)	248 (39)
H (O* 1)	8450 (27)	32468 (32)	6516 (35)	854 (23)	995 (35)	1489 (42)	-138 (23)	508 (26)	-209 (30)
H (O* 3)	-3100 (24)	40891 (30)	17613 (35)	716 (21)	677 (26)	1589 (44)	85 (19)	327 (24)	159 (28)
H (O* 4)	-1672 (25)	15381 (34)	-19611 (27)	849 (23)	1109 (33)	729 (30)	-4 (23)	45 (21)	47 (25)
H (O* 6)	34766 (29)	27404 (37)	16026 (35)	909 (26)	1261 (39)	1234 (40)	-211 (26)	287 (27)	-199 (32)

Software developed in the 60s/70s to check for errors in retyping coordinates (or in the original literature) formed to foundation of early data curation tools

Data from Brown & Levy (1973) Acta Crystallogr., Sect. B: Struct. Crystallogr. Cryst. Chem

Data Journey of a Crystal Structure

Data captured in a standard semantic formats

Deposition of data in a crystallographic data repository

Enrichment of data by expert data curators

Ongoing enhancements to address changing needs

Publication

CCDC

Facets of a {Crystallography} Experiment

Sample

Synthesis
Crystallisation
Recrystallisation

Crystal Properties
Chemical Properties
Chemical Identity

Equipment

Make, model etc.
Radiation Type
Configuration
Ambient Conditions

Data

Raw data
Processed data
Derived data

Unit Cell
Symmetry
Atom coordinates
Quality metrics

Software

Versions used
Parameters specified
Restrains used

Publication

research communications
Crystal structure of [2,13-bis(acetamido)-5,16-dimethyl-2,6,13,17-tetraazatricyclo[16.4.0.0¹²]-docosane-*N*²/silver(II) dinitrate from synchrotron X-ray data

Dohyun Moon^a and Jung-Ha Choi^{b*}
^aPolymers and Composites Laboratory, POSTECH, Pohang 707-370, Republic of Korea, and ^bDepartment of Chemistry, Andong National University, Andong 36729, Republic of Korea. *Correspondence e-mail: jhchoi@anu.ac.kr
The asymmetric unit of the title compound, [Ag(C₁₄H₂₀N₄O₂)₂(NO₃)₂], consists of one independent half of the [Ag(C₁₄H₂₀N₄O₂)₂]²⁺ cation and one nitrate anion. The Ag atom, lying on an inversion centre, has a square planar geometry and the complex adopts a stable *trans*-[III] conformation. Interestingly, the two O atoms of the pendant acetamide groups are not coordinated to the Ag⁺ ion. The longer distance of 2.227 (3) Å for Ag⁺–N(secondary) compared to 2.134 (2) Å for Ag⁺–N(tertiary) may be due to the effects of the attached acetamide group on the tertiary N atom. Two nitrate anions are very weakly bonded to the Ag⁺ ion in the axial sites and are further connected to the ligand of the cation by N–H...O hydrogen bonds. The crystal packing is stabilised by hydrogen-bonding interactions among the N–H donor groups of the macrocycle and its acetamide substituents, and the O atoms of the nitrate anions and of an acetamide group on the acceptor atoms.

Article Content
Article Reference
Related Citations
Peer Review
Data Repository ID
Database Entry

CIF – The *lingua franca* of Crystallography

```

CCDC 252295: doi:10.5517/cc8gjks
cell_length_b          8.3463(7)
cell
cell
CCDC 917625: doi:10.5517/cczsvtd
cell_refine_ls_wR_factor_ref      0.1665
cell_refine_ls_wR_factor_gt       0.1240
cell_ref
cell_ref
CCDC 933841: doi:10.5517/cc10bqxz
exp_ref_diffn_source              'Enraf Nonius FR590'
exp_ref_diffn_ambient_temperature 293(2)
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exp_com_diffn_radiation_type       MoK $\alpha$ 
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exp_com_diffn_radiation_probe      x-ray
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ato_com_refine_ls_matrix_type       full
ato_refine_ls_weighting_scheme      cal $\chi$ 
ato_refine_ls_hydrogen_treatment    mixed
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ato_ato_atom_site_adp_type
ato_ato_atom_site_occupancy
O1 O ato_atom_site_symmetry_multiplicity
H1 H ato_atom_site_calc_flag
C1 C ato_atom_site_refinement_flags
C2 C ato_atom_site_disorder_assembly
H2A ato_atom_site_disorder_group
H2E C1 C2 C 0.25054(14) 0.43179(18) 0.0354(4) 0.0479(7) Uani 1 1 d . . .
H2 H 0.2161 0.3958 -0.0319 0.057 Uiso 1 1 calc R . .
C3 C C2 C 0.31582(17) 0.4034(2) -0.2628(5) 0.0667(10) Uani 1 1 d . . .
H3A H2 H H4A H 0.2787 0.3685 -0.313 0.08 Uiso 1 1 calc R . .
H3E C3 C H4B H 0.3337 0.4248 -0.3705 0.08 Uiso 1 1 calc R . .
C4 C C6 C 0.3379(2) 0.3078(2) -0.0106(6) 0.0682(10) Uani 1 1 d . . .
H4A C4 C C7 C 0.42890(17) 0.3945(2) -0.0854(6) 0.0714(11) Uani 1 1 d . . .
C5 C H7 H 0.4213 0.4391 0.0007 0.086 Uiso 1 1 calc R . .
H5A C6 C C8 C 0.4788(2) 0.3353(4) 0.0224(9) 0.143(2) Uani 1 1 d . . .
H5E C7 C H8A H 0.4655 0.321 0.141 0.215 Uiso 1 1 calc R . .
H7 H H8B H 0.5216 0.3607 0.0465 0.215 Uiso 1 1 calc R . .
C6 C H8C H 0.4808 0.2867 -0.0523 0.215 Uiso 1 1 calc R . .
H6E H8 C9 C 0.4558(2) 0.4305(4) -0.2510(9) 0.129(2) Uani 1 1 d . . .
H8 H H9A H 0.4591 0.3883 -0.3428 0.193 Uiso 1 1 calc R . .
C9 C H9B H 0.4988 0.4532 -0.207 0.193 Uiso 1 1 calc R . .
C10 H9C H 0.4267 0.4728 -0.3088 0.193 Uiso 1 1 calc R . .
C10 C 0.27717(13) 0.59110(18) 0.3750(4) 0.0411(7) Uani 1 1 d . . .

```

Data are typically deposited with the CCDC in CIF format: **Semantic representation of crystallographic data including**

- Details of the sample
- Equipment details
- Experimental conditions
- Software packages and parameters used
- Raw, processed and derived data
- Publication details

Crystal structure refinement software allows researchers to save CIFs with much of this data

Developed and
maintained by the
IUCr

The Crystallographic
Information File (CIF)
A community standard

<https://www.iucr.org/resources/cif>

checkCIF

A service hosted by the IUCr that highlights potential problems with a particular dataset

- Required data that is missing
- Inconsistencies in the data
- Whether the structural model is potentially incorrect
- Indicators relating to the quality of the structure

checkCIF generates alerts of varying severity that should either be addressed or explained

<https://doi.org/10.1107/S2056989019016244>

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crystals
an open access journal by Wiley

A service of the
International Union of Crystallography

checkCIF reports on the consistency and integrity of crystal structure determinations reported in CIF format.

Please upload your CIF using the form below.

File name:
Choose file No file chosen

Select form of checkCIF report

HTML

PDF

PDF email (recommended for CIFs that might take a long time to check)

Select validation type

Full validation of CIF and structure factors

Full IUCr publication validation of CIF and structure factors

Validation of CIF only (no structure factors)

Output Validation Response Form

Level A alerts only

Level A and B alerts

Level A, B and C alerts

None

Send CIF for checking

This version of checkCIF includes checks on:

- CIF syntax and construction
- Cell and geometry details
- Space-group symmetry
- Anisotropic displacement parameters
- Structure factors

Useful links

Prepublication check for submissions to IUCr journals

Details of checkCIF/PLATON tests

CIF dictionary

Download CIF editor (publCIF) from the IUCr

Download CIF editor (enCIFer) from the CCDC

CCDC

Joint CSD/ICSD web deposition service

<https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/deposit>

CIF deposition and validation service

First name(s)

Last name(s)

Your email address

Your ORCID ID [Create or Connect your ORCID ID](#)

Additional email addresses Please add any additional email addresses

Institution (e.g. University/Company) ccdc

Deposition number(s) for revision

CIF/HKL/RES/FCF/Word/ZIP files
 Y1GPI003.cif 4.42 KB

Details Remember my details

Options I wish to run the IUCr *checkCIF/PLATON* service on my data

Tailored web deposition service enabling scientists to deposit crystal structures ready for publication

Multi-stage deposition progress helps scientists check and enhance their data

- Syntax checking
- Validation
- Enrichment

Validation: checkCIF

Validation

View reports on the consistency and integrity of your structures

Structure	IUCr checkCIF
structure01.cif	
data_l	View Report <input style="border: 1px solid #ccc; width: 60px;" type="text" value="Enter Response"/>
structure02.cif	
data_sa2906c	View Report <input style="border: 1px solid #ccc; width: 60px;" type="text" value="Enter Response"/>
data_sa2906a	View Report <input style="border: 1px solid #ccc; width: 60px;" type="text" value="Enter Response"/>
data_sa2906b	View Report <input style="border: 1px solid #ccc; width: 60px;" type="text" value="Enter Response"/>
data_sa2906g	View Report <input style="border: 1px solid #ccc; width: 60px;" type="text" value="No Response Required"/>

CheckCIF Responses:

▼ Level A

PLAT027 _diffn_reflns_theta_full value (too) Low 13.50 Degree

PLAT029 _diffn_measured_fraction_theta_full value Low . 0.677 Note

▼ Level B

PLAT415 Short Inter D-H..H-X H1 .. H623 .. 2.00 Ang.

> Level C

- Explanations of checkCIF alerts can be included directly in a CIF.
- The CCDC deposition service enables this.

Validation: Duplicate Check

Validation

View reports on the consistency and integrity of your structures

Structure	IUCr checkCIF	Unit cell check
structure01.cif		
data_I	View Report <input type="text" value="Enter Response"/>	View Hits
structure02.cif		
data_sa2906c	View Report <input type="text" value="Enter Response"/>	View Hits
data_sa2906a	View Report <input type="text" value="Enter Response"/>	View Hits
data_sa2906b	View Report <input type="text" value="Enter Response"/>	View Hits
data_sa2906g	View Report <input type="text" value="No Response Required"/>	View Hits

- Deposition process includes a check that can identify prior determinations of the same structure

FAMCUU		Deposition Number(s): 1501474 Space Group: P 2 ₁ 2 ₁ 2 ₁ (19) Cell: a 6.9209(2)Å b 10.5769(2)Å c 15.4237(4)Å, α 90° β 90° γ 90°
FINXAD		Deposition Number(s): 912870 Space Group: P 2 ₁ 2 ₁ 2 ₁ (19) Cell: a 6.991(5)Å b 10.778(5)Å c 15.575(5)Å, α 90.00° β 90.00° γ 90.00°
GIDXUM		Deposition Number(s): 1167512 Space Group: P 2 ₁ 2 ₁ 2 ₁ (19) Cell: a 6.844(2)Å b 10.975(5)Å c 15.363(5)Å, α 90° β 90° γ 90°
KELCAH		Deposition Number(s): 886135 Space Group: P 2 ₁ 2 ₁ 2 ₁ (19) Cell: a 6.953(1)Å b 10.665(2)Å c 15.414(3)Å, α 90° β 90° γ 90°

Enhance Data

Pick a structure to edit

- example_cif.cif
- data_test_data

3D viewer

JSmol

Chemical diagram

Formula moiety

C12 F4 N4

Formula sum

C12 F4 N4

Melting point (K)

Crystallisation method

Crystallisation source

Physical properties

- Magnetic properties
- Luminescent
- Other: please specify below

Additional refinement details

- Twin
- SQUEEZE
- Other: please specify below

Additional comments

data_test_data

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1 data_test_data
2
3 _audit_creation_date 2019-03-26
4 _audit_creation_method
5
6 Olex2 1.2
7 (compiled 2018.05.29 svn.r3508 for OlexSys, GUI svn.r5506)
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9 _shelx_SHELXL_version_number '2018/3'
10 _audit_contact_author_address ?
11 _audit_contact_author_email ?
12 _audit_contact_author_name ?
13 _audit_contact_author_phone ?
14 _publ_contact_author_id_orcid ?
15 _publ_section_references
16 Dolomanov, O.V., Bourhis, I.J., Gildea, R.J., Howard, J.A.K. & Puschmann, H.
17 (2009), I. Appl. Cryst. 42, 339-341.
18
19 Sheldrick, G.M. (2015), Acta Cryst. A71, 3-8.
20
21 Sheldrick, G.M. (2015), Acta Cryst. C71, 3-8.
22
23
24 _chemical_name_common ?
25 _chemical_name_systematic
26 2,3,5,6-tetrafluoro-7,7,8,8-tetracyanoquinodimethane
27 _chemical_formula_moiety 'C12 F4 N4'
28 _chemical_formula_sum 'C12 F4 N4'
29 _chemical_formula_weight 276.16
30 _chemical_melting_point ?
31 loop
32 _atom_type_symbol
33 _atom_type_description
34 _atom_type_scat_dispersion_real
35 _atom_type_scat_dispersion_imag
36 _atom_type_scat_source
37 'C' 'C' 0.0015 0.0009 'International Tables Vol C Tables 4.2.6.8 and 6.1.1.4'
38 'N' 'N' 0.0030 0.0019 'International Tables Vol C Tables 4.2.6.8 and 6.1.1.4'
39 'F' 'F' 0.0096 0.0061 'International Tables Vol C Tables 4.2.6.8 and 6.1.1.4'

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Data fields

Compound name

2,3,5,6-tetrafluoro-7,7,8,8-tetracyanoquinodimethane

Synonyms/other names

Crystal colour

greenish yellow

Crystal habit

Space group

P n n m

Study temperature (K)

100.0

Sensitivity

- Air-sensitive
- Moisture-sensitive
- Hygroscopic
- Efflorescent
- Deliquescent
- Heat-sensitive
- Oxygen-sensitive
- Light-sensitive
- Photo-sensitive
- Pyrophoric
- Other: please specify below

Data Journey of a Crystal Structure

Data captured in a standard semantic formats

Deposition of data in a crystallographic data repository

Enrichment of data by expert data curators

Ongoing enhancements to address changing needs

Publication

CCDC

Enabling Data Discovery and Reuse

- Providing a 2D chemical interpretation of 3D experimental data
- Combination of automated and manual processing

<https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/Community/blog/CSD-data-curation-the-human-touch/>

Automatic Assignment of Chemistry

For a structure without bond types assigned, bond type suggested by geometry may be different to bond type typically assigned in the CSD.

Competing Evidence

C=C, prob = 0.20

2 hits

C-C, prob = 0.004

7208 hits

Bayes' Theorem

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(B|A) P(A)}{P(B)}$$

Different and sometimes conflicting observations from the CSD are fed in to Bayes Theorem to identify the most likely assignment

Automatic Assignment of Chemistry

Reliability Flags consider:

- Presence of metal
- Low probability bond lengths
- Unusual oxidation states
- Unusual pattern of missing H
- Non planar double/aromatic bonds

Combining Automation and Expert Validation

```

loop_
_atom_site_label
_atom_site_type_symbol
_atom_site_fract_x
_atom_site_fract_y
_atom_site_fract_z
_atom_site_U_iso_or_equiv
_atom_site_adp_type
_atom_site_occupancy
_atom_site_symmetry_multiplicity
_atom_site_calc_flag
_atom_site_refinement_flags
_atom_site_disorder_assembly
_atom_site_disorder_group
C11 C1 0.5993(2) 1.0007(7) 0.8131(17) 0.044(3) Uani 0.50 1 d PDU A 1
S1 S 0.5321(3) 0.8260(6) 0.9322(3) 0.0327(11) Uani 0.50 1 d PDU A 1
C2 C 0.5529(4) 0.8802(9) 0.8184(9) 0.029(4) Uani 0.50 1 d PDU A 1
C3 C 0.5286(7) 0.8174(18) 0.7440(7) 0.031(4) Uani 0.50 1 d PDU A 1
H3A H 0.5350 0.8343 0.6771 0.037 Uiso 0.50 1 calc PR A 1
C4 C 0.4918(8) 0.7220(19) 0.7783(8) 0.027(4) Uani 0.50 1 d PDU A 1
C5 C 0.4900(6) 0.7171(14) 0.8779(9) 0.029(4) Uani 0.50 1 d PDU A 1
C12 C1 0.3202(2) 0.4982(6) 1.0830(5) 0.0586(15) Uani 0.50 1 d PDU A 1
S2 S 0.38755(19) 0.6658(5) 0.9578(5) 0.0400(10) Uani 0.50 1 d PDU A 1
    
```


Reliability reports from automated processes help prioritise manual validation of structures.

Newly validated structures add to the body of knowledge used to process future structures.

CSD NIWBIH

Asymmetric unit with disordered atoms hidden

Facets of a CSD Entry

```

C2 C 0.19196(41) 0.77066(23) 0.76436(17)
O1 O 0.22259(32) 0.80293(21) 0.83459(13)
C3 C 0.03051(40) 0.74837(26) 0.73926(18)
H1 H -0.05699(40) 0.75110(25) 0.77720(18)
C4 C -0.00500(38) 0.71111(22) 0.66463(17)
H2 H -0.11609(38) 0.69111(22) 0.65036(17)
N1 N 0.11523(28) 0.68419(17) 0.60921(13)
C5 C 0.27057(33) 0.61113(20) 0.62788(16)
H3 H 0.5291(33) 0.70477(20) 0.58724(16)
C6 C 0.7764(37) 0.5275(21) 0.52604(17)
H4 H 0.71111(22) 0.496(17)
O2 O -0.08111(22) 0.51626(12)
C7 C -0.14566(36) 0.51798(21) 0.51434(17)
H5 H -0.17523(36) 0.51111(21) 0.51111(17)
C8 C -0.00156(37) 0.41146(20) 0.51111(16)
H6 H 0.00432(37) 0.48356(20) 0.60532(16)
O3 O -0.00111(36) 0.39311(14) 0.51111(11)
C9 C 0.14111(38) 0.54908(21) 0.51111(15)
H7 H 0.24111(38) 0.53822(21) 0.51111(15)
O4 O 0.17120(25) 0.52534(11) 0.41111(11)
C10 C 0.49371(42) 0.77147(21) 0.71438(18)
N2 N 0.53197(39) 0.80044(26) 0.79008(19)
H8 H 0.3795(48) 0.8122(26) 0.8171(20)
H9 H 0.6222(50) 0.8122(26) 0.7999(22)
O5 O 0.
  
```


Associated publications

 G.Bringmann, M.Ochse, K.Wolf, J.Kraus, K.Peters, E.-M.Peters, M.Herderich, L.Ake Assi, F.S.K.Tayman, *Phytochemistry*, 1999, 51, 271, DOI: 10.1016/S0031-9422(98)00752-3

Chemical details

Formula C₁₇ H₂₀ N₂ O₉

Melting Point 471-474 K

Crystal details

Space group P 2₁ 2₁ 2₁ (19)

Unit cell a 8.218(2)Å b 13.783(3)Å c 16.303(3)Å
α 90° β 90° γ 90°

Cell volume 1846.62

Reduced cell a 8.218Å b 13.783Å c 16.303Å
α 90.000° β 90.000° γ 90.000°

Z, Z' 4, 1

Habit needles

Colour colorless

Natural source Rothmannia longiflora Salisb. (Rubiaceae)

Experimental details

R-factor (%) 5.06

Temperature (K) 295

Density (CCDC) 1.426

Radiation probe x-ray

Experiment type single crystal

Additional details

Deposition Number 109904

Data Citation G.Bringmann, M.Ochse, K.Wolf, J.Kraus, K.Peters, E.-M.Peters, M.Herderich, L.Ake Assi, F.S.K.Tayman CCDC 109904: Experimental Crystal Structure Determination, 1999, DOI: 10.5517/cc3pc9f

Deposited on 09/11/1999

```

H12 H 0.11111(22) 0.51111(11)
H13 H -0.29520(57) 0.60212(31) 0.79458(20)
H14 H -0.27668(57) 0.48892(31) 0.79514(20)
C14 C 0.08304(42) 0.32837(23) 0.55160(18)
O8 O 0.17917(29) 0.34886(16) 0.60310(13)
  
```

CSD Entry: BASYOJ

<https://identifiers.org/csd:BASYOJ>

Revisiting CSD entries

Targeted improvements allow improved integrity, consistency, discoverability and value of data

Creation and maintenance of subsets

Standardisation of early CSD entries

Improving visual representations

Investigating structures with unusually large atomic displacement parameters

Fixing structural diagrams with coincident atoms

Enhancing Entries

Standardising text fields e.g. habit, colour

Labelling polymorphs in CSD Drug Subset

Data Curation Enablers

- Standard semantic file formats **widely adopted by key software tools and platforms**
- Guidance, best practice and services **promoted by IUCr and adopted by publishers**
- Data deposition workflows **encouraging best practice by researchers** and connecting to publication platforms
- Automated tools that enable **triage necessary to prioritise manual curation** in the face of increasing throughput
- Considering **curation throughout the data lifecycle** – from data generation through publication and beyond

Acknowledgements

All who contribute to the development and adoption of standards, tools and services featured in this talk.

The CCDC Data & Community team who make the curation happen.

<https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/>

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bruno@ccdc.cam.ac.uk

The collage includes several key elements:

- Microscope:** Shows yellow crystals on a slide.
- Diffraction Pattern:** A 2D plot of intensity versus scattering angle.
- 3D Molecular Model:** A ball-and-stick model of a molecule with green and blue atoms.
- CIF Deposition Form:** A screenshot of the 'CIF deposition and validation service' interface, showing fields for name, email, and company.
- Chemical Structure:** A 2D chemical structure of a substituted benzene ring with labels like 'NC', 'CN', 'F', and 'other'.
- Histogram:** A plot of 'Mogul search - Torsion angle - O3P P O4P CSA' showing a distribution of torsion angles.
- Data Table:** A table with columns for 'data_polyorph_1' and various crystallographic parameters such as 'cell_length_a', 'cell_length_b', 'cell_length_c', 'cell_angle_alpha', etc.

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(A, B)}{P(B)}$$